

HISTORY
OF
GEOLOGY
GROUP

GeoHistories

Unlocking Lapworth's Legacy p. 9

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GeoHistories

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Editorial

I hope it wasn't presumptuous to take as a compliment a recent description of *GeoHistories* as an 'eclectic' mix. Among the several words of definition in the (Shorter) OED, the word eclectic is defined as 'Broad, not exclusive'. And that, I feel, is very much what HOGG and, by extension, *GeoHistories* is all about. But another 'e' word that might possibly be used of the group and its magazine is 'esoteric', a word defined *inter alia* as 'Not openly avowed; pertaining to a select circle'. In HOGG's case the circle is not so much 'select' as 'self-selecting', being a group of otherwise disparate individuals who share an interest in one or more aspects of the history of geological science.

It is therefore a great joy to me that this edition of *GeoHistories* contains so much evidence of the varied enthusiasms of HOGG's members. The accounts of three recent online lunchtime talks, by Richard Edmonds, Rachel Brown and Peter Riches, are each the result of long and dedicated studies on the part of their authors. These accounts are followed by reviews of three books, of which two were written by HOGG members, Roy Starkey and Nina Morgan—once again demonstrating enormous commitment to their chosen subject.

John Henry reports on what we might call an episode of outreach, as our chairperson, Duncan Hawley introduces the wider membership of the Geological Society to the various editions of the Society's 'own' geological map of England and Wales. Then Duncan himself provides a fitting celebration of the bicentenary of another seminal publication: Conybeare and Phillips' *Outlines*.

Four articles follow, demonstrating the enthusiasms of Tom Sharpe, Douglas Palmer and Phil James. These cover a full range of topics: artifacts, people and events—the latter being a timely celebration of the first ascent of Everest, almost exactly 70 years ago as we go to press.

Wendy Cawthorne offers a most important exhibit for our Cabinet of Curiosities, complete with a fascinating story of its provenance, and I was delighted that Jim Secord could find time during his busy period as president of the British Society for the History of Science to submit himself to the intense scrutiny of a HoG's Life interview! Finally, as ever, Nina Morgan rounds things off—this time with a slightly 'sideways' view of Mary Anning.

Clearly HOGG members remain as busy and as enthusiastic as ever, exploring many and various aspects of the history of geology. Some may think this an esoteric study, but within HOGG you are among friends. Please consider sharing your work and helping to ensure that future issues of *GeoHistories* remain a truly eclectic mix.

Peter Lincoln
hoggnewsletter@gmail.com

I will start by paying tribute to two members, sadly no longer with us, who contributed to history of geology, albeit in different ways. Many of you will know Beris Cox, at least by name, as, for many years, she edited the HOGG newsletter. Beris knew her history of geology stuff too.

Last year she was due to give a presentation to an INHIGEO webinar on the 1888 International Congress of Geology held in London. Although, alas, she was not well enough to present, the accompanying article was published in the journal *Episodes*. It is available online at <https://tinyurl.com/7ethwdjr>.

Professor Ron Austin was, arguably, more parochial. Swansea-based, he did much to promote the history underpinning the geological heritage of that city (which boasts William Logan, H.T. De La Beche, and the Ladies of Penrice amongst its luminaries) and to ensure that history of geology was noticed. Fuller obituaries will appear in the next issue of *GeoHistories*.

Both Beris and Ron would be pleased to know that HOGG continues to thrive. Membership numbers are relatively stable and dues have now been paid—thank you to all. By prudent use of funds the HOGG Committee has managed to keep the subscription fee at £15 (yet again) and just £5 for a Young member. We hope you think this is good value for money and we encourage you to encourage others to join the group—it would be good to see an uptick on the membership graph.

Behind the scenes it is the dedication of the HOGG committee and their willingness to take on some voluntary duties that keeps HOGG alive and thriving. There is a pressing concern for members to step forward and volunteer to help move HOGG forward, otherwise the responsibility

for HOGG activity and management falls on too few shoulders, with the inevitable strains that brings. The ‘three-years service’ clause in our constitution means there is a constant need for ‘new blood’, and such renewal also brings in new experience, new ideas and new skills. We also need co-opted members, who take on specific tasks. We really do need your help, so please email me and declare you are willing!

One task that is nearly complete is the upgrade to the HOGG website. The old site had become ‘clunky’ and it was difficult to upload content. The revamped site should be up and running very shortly. It will be easier to keep up-to-date, with news of meetings, and other information of interest to members. One new benefit will be a members-only section making it easier to register for meetings and events and to access videos of past meetings. There are also plans to add more member features. We owe a big thank you to Consuelo Sendino, who has driven the changes and taken on the responsibility of HOGG web-maestro. We hope that the HOGG website will be a regular place for you to visit when you switch on your computer or mobile.

I’ll finish with a Twitter tale (by the way, do look in on the HOGG Twitter feed: <https://twitter.com/HOGGGroup> or @HOGGGroup—there are regular snippets celebrating or relating to interesting people and events across the history of geology). Recently, I was reminded of the importance of context when interpreting meaning in history of geology via a video posted by ‘MyDearDarwin’ – the Twitter feed of the Darwin Correspondence Project. The short (one minute) video can be seen here: <https://tinyurl.com/yvnasbfd>.

The message?—Always try to get inside the mind of geologists and take their actions and ideas in the context of what was known and the standards of the day, not by what we know now!

Duncan Hawley
duncan.hawley.hogg@gmail.com

AGM November 2022 – Secretary’s Report

The 2022 AGM was held online on 22nd November 2022

The group’s acting secretary, Duncan Hawley, outlined the year’s activity in this report.

Secretary’s Annual Report 2022

Events:

Online meetings have become an established and regular feature of the HOGG events programme, but there was also a return to the field with two meetings taking place ‘en plein air’.

All online meetings and events have been free of charge to HOGG members, with admission to friends and associates for a small fee that covers admin costs.

The AGM in 2021 was followed by a talk on *Discovering the first true Silurian: following in the footsteps of Murchison*, by Chairperson Duncan Hawley.

Six lunchtime (13.00–14.00hrs) sessions were organised, with each session followed by a Q&A.

17th February: *The A to Z of Toxic Rocks across time* with Tim Carter

17th March - *Lyell, Darwin and the principle of reasoning in geology*, with Gordon Chancellor.

21st April: *Andrew Crombie Ramsay: insights into mid-19th century geology from his papers archive*, with Anne Barrett

23rd June: *Sedgwick's 'Great Dislocation' revisited: the Dent Fault, N W England*, with Dr. Nigel Woodcock

17th September: *The Great Bindon Landslip of 1839 -finally a modern interpretation?*, with Richard Edmonds

20th October: *Unlocking Lapworth's Legacy: archiving the life and work of a Victorian Geologist*, with Rachel Brown.

The meetings were held on the opensource *Jitsi* platform at no cost. All registrations for meetings was organised through the Eventbrite events platform, which reduced administrative chores and enabled access to basic analytics.

Numbers registered/attending ranged from 34 to 65, with an average of 46.

All meetings were recorded and placed in a HOGG Google Drive account for members to view, by streaming or download, at their leisure. Moreover, each presenter agreed to write a short summary article for *GeoHistories* magazine.

Thanks are due to all those people who generously presented talks during 2022.

Two field meetings took place.

May 20th-22nd *Malvern Rocks! Geology in a Victorian Health Resort*, convened by Tim Carter and organised and supported by local experts from the Hereford & Worcester Earth Heritage Trust. This was a re-convened meeting from 2021. Seven members attended and the meeting was a great success. A comprehensive field booklet was produced and distributed, with a pdf version made available via the H&W EHT.

July 15th-17th *Pioneer geological mapping of Anglesey: the work of John Stevens Henslow, Andrew Crombie Ramsay and Edward Greenly*, convened by Duncan Hawley and Cynthia Burek, organised with support of the GeoMoñ (Anglesey) GeoPark. Eleven members attended. The meeting was a success, with explorations across the island of the work of all three pioneers, although the record-breaking heatwave weather impacted in that not all planned locations were visited. A comprehensive field booklet was produced and distributed.

Membership

There were 178 members during 2022, of whom eight joined during the year.

The membership is drawn from a wide range of backgrounds with a diversity of interests in the history of geology.

We are sorry to report the death of two members during the years, Stuart Baldwin and Dr Peter Sabine, and obituary notices were published in *GeoHistories* magazine.

Committee Business

HOGG Committee met five times over the year (January, March, July, September, November). All meetings were online.

Duncan Hawley agreed to serve on HOGG Committee as Chairperson for the year and also as Acting Secretary. He is due to stand down from these roles at the end of 2022.

The HOGG Committee comprised eleven members, falling one short of the full complement of twelve.

Over the year HOGG Committee has engaged with our 'parent' affiliate, The Geological Society, with Andrew Hopkins as representative on the Geological Society Memorialization Working Group (MWG). HOGG contributed to the final report and recommendations of the MWG to the Geological Society Council, that take historical context into account when considering potential issues related to historical archives, artefacts and artwork.

The HOGG Committee was pleased to nominate Professor John Mather for the Sue Tyler Friedman Award of the Geological Society of London. This award is given to an individual who is deemed to have made a significant contribution to the history of geoscience. We were delighted to learn that John was selected to receive this award and his award citation and response is available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=49gw2OrNtEQ> (from 42m:42s on)

Several HOGG Committee members are completing their term of office this year:

- Peter Riches has served as Secretary from 2019-2020 and from 2021-2022
- Tim Carter brought a non-geologist's perspective to the Committee, together with wisdom and experience of serving on the committees of several other bodies.
- Duncan Hawley has served on HOGG Committee since 2017, and as Chairperson since 2018. He oversaw HOGG's 25th anniversary celebrations and latterly steered HOGG through the pandemic period, establishing online continuity of HOGG activities.
- Sarah Scott served as the Geological Society's representative and liaison on HOGG Committee until her retirement from the GSL Council in June. The incoming representative is Dr Jennie Gilbert.

We are very grateful for the service and dedication they have all offered to HOGG over the last three or more years.

Online activity and Social Media

HOGG has a firm but modest presence online.

The JISCmail general discussion and message forum is available to HOGG members and associates.

HOGG Committee agreed to contract upgrade of the HOGG website to Tolstow Design and the process is now underway. New features, including an exclusive members' area, will be available when the upgrade is completed. This work meant the website was temporarily not available for a short period in September. The website is now managed by Dr Consuelo Sendino.

The HOGG website was previously maintained by arrangement with Barbara Silva, and thanks are due for her service to HOGG over the last five years.

The HOGG Twitter feed has 2,600 followers (400+ up on 2021) and has been active throughout 2022. Posts include a few original tweets but generally are re-tweets of other posts of interest to HOGG members. These are accessed by following @HOGG, via the HOGG website or the HOGG page on the Geological Society website.

Publications

a) HOGG Bulletin

Seven issues, from No.8 through to No.14, with updates and listing of events, publications and other news from HOGG and the wider history of geology community were published during 2022 and distributed to all HOGG members and HOGG associates. Thanks are due to Andrew Hopkins who coordinates collation of entries and distribution of the Bulletin.

b) *GeoHistories*

Two issues of the HOGG Magazine, Nos. 73 and 74 (each 36 pages, including covers) were published and distributed to members. The issues contained the 'proceedings' of HOGG events, with summaries by presenters or attendees, plus a range of regular features. The high quality of the magazine was retained. Distribution was eased by integration with

printing. Thanks are due to Peter Lincoln, editor of *GeoHistories* and to Consuelo Sendino for her support in design and layout. *GeoHistories* is a member-only publication and is not made available more widely, with the exception of a copy deposited in the Geological Society Library.

History of Geology community matters

A report of HOGG activities for 2021 was included in the INHIGEO (International Commission on the History of Geological Sciences) Annual Record No.54, available from the INHIGEO website www.inhigeo.com/index.html

HOGG was a signatory to a letter, organised by the Edinburgh Geological Society to Historic Environment Scotland, querying the on-going closure of access to Hutton's Section on the Radical Road of Salisbury Crags, Edinburgh, and requesting a plan for re-opening access.

The HOGG Committee organised a birthday card for Martin Rudwick to celebrate his 90th birthday.

Duncan Hawley
HOGG Acting Secretary

November 2022

Financial Statement

HOGG Financial Statement 2022			
Financial Year: 30 th September 2021 to 30 th October 2022			
Income	£	Expenses	£
Subscriptions*	2,730	Donations	
Meeting registrations	379	Bulletin/ <i>GeoHistories</i>	2,310
		Field Meetings	266
		Website	771
		Insurance	144
		Zoom Licence	
		GA Affiliation	40
		Paypal charges	31
		Misc.	13
Total Income	3,109	Total expenses	3,574
*Paid up members 178			
Income minus Expenses - £465			
Bank Balances	30/10/2022	30/09/2021	change
	£	£	£
Santander	12,407	12,872	(465)
Paypal	-	-	-
Total	12,407	12,872	-465

The accounts for 2022 are for 13 months compared to 12 months for the previous year.

The current cash balance in the Santander Bank account is £12,407 and expenditure for the year exceeded income by £465.

Income is overwhelmingly from membership subscriptions. The two field meetings this year (none in 2021) provided a surplus of £37 and a further £76 came from non-members' fees for watching online lectures.

No donations were made this year.

The major expenditure was for the production and distribution of our magazine *GeoHistories*, plus a very minor amount for the Bulletins. Website expenses are for its registration and maintenance. PayPal fees are for processing membership subscriptions paid for online through PayPal. As a result of our affiliation with the Geologists' Association, we are able to obtain our insurance through them. The insurance expenses for 2022 are half those of 2021 as the 2021 payment covered premiums for two years.

P. Riches
Hon. Treasurer

2nd November 2022

Committee News

HOGG Committee 2023

Duncan Hawley (Chairperson and acting Secretary & Treasurer)

Committee members: Anne Barrett, Jay Bosanquet, Gordon Chancellor, Andrew Hopkins (**Bulletin**), Cindy Howells, Piotr Krzywiec, Peter Lincoln (**GeoHistories & Membership**), Consuelo Sendino (**Website**)

At the 2021 AGM we thanked retiring committee members Tim Carter, Peter Riches and Sarah Scott and welcomed:

Piotr Krzywiec

Piotr Krzywiec studied at the Jagiellonian University and the AGH Univ. of Science & Technology, both Kraków, Poland, and at Imperial College, London, UK. He holds MSc in Geology, and MSc and PhD in Exploration Geophysics. Piotr worked for 16 years at the Polish Geological Institute (i.e. the Polish Geological Survey), since 2012 he has been Associate Professor at

the Institute of Geological Sciences of the Polish Academy of

Sciences, Warsaw, Poland. He is also external lecturer in Geophysics / Seismic Methods at the Jagiellonian University (Kraków) and the Adam Mickiewicz University (Poznań), and lectures world-wide within the AAPG Visiting Geoscientist Program that he currently co-chairs. His main research interests are in integrated analysis of geophysical and geological data, basin analysis, tectonics, seismic stratigraphy, and history of geology in all forms and shapes. He is author or co-author of 200+ peer-reviewed papers or book chapters. Piotr is active member of the Polish Geological Society (currently co-chair of Section of History of Earth Sciences and Secretary of the Board), European Geosciences Union, American Association of Petroleum Geologists (until recently he co-chaired the AAPG Committee on History of Petroleum Geology), Society of Exploration Geophysicists, History of Earth Sciences Society, Petroleum History Institute and INHIGEO (International Commission on the History of Geological Sciences). Piotr is also an avid collector of old geological books and maps, with special focus on the territory of Poland and adjacent countries and regions.

Members' News

R.I.P.

Roy McIntyre (1930-2022)

Roy McIntyre became a HOGG member late in life. It was through his late wife Elizabeth's involvement in the West of England GA that he became interested in geology following his retirement in 1991 after 37 years with Rolls Royce. In 2015, the bicentenary year of William Smith's map, they joined HOGG and attended our meeting at the archive of Bristol University, near their home. Roy became hooked on

William Smith's maps, which after Elizabeth's death became, in his own modest words, his hobby.

This hobby focused Roy's keen observational and reasoning skills as a retired aeronautical engineer and Chartered Mathematician, his considerable knowledge of the North of England, where he was born and grew up in and around the Tyneside colliery village of Whitburn, and his experience, as a keen walker and photographer, of the landscape of the Borderlands of Scotland and England. Roy scrutinised Smith's maps—the surviving manuscript field maps of Durham and Northumberland, and all his published maps: both county maps

and the parts of the national maps depicting that region and Scotland. Images of faint pencilled annotations and partly legible inked notes bounced between us during the pandemic as we attempted to decipher them. For context, Roy scoured Phillip's memoir and Smith's own diary as well as contemporary geological maps and reports. He was able to trace, better than anyone so far, where Smith had been and the way he connected his field observations and contemporary sources. His work resulted in a well-illustrated presentation at HOGG's Edinburgh meeting in 2019 and three papers in *Earth Sciences History (ESH)* 39/1 pp 64-87, and 88-98, and t.b.a.), with the final paper being submitted in the fortnight before he died. To come new to a subject and to confidently publish in one's final decade is a remarkable achievement.

Roy enjoyed the strong support of a close family. He and Elizabeth were married for over 60 years. The Edinburgh meeting was the occasion for a McIntyre reunion; his sons assisted with the presentation and illustration of his paper. Roy often attached photographs of long-ago hill walks to illustrate points on Smith's maps. These always included Elizabeth. Latterly, he sent current photos of family gatherings which he enjoyed immensely. Roy leaves his daughter Nancy and sons, Graham, David and Colin, six grandchildren and a great-grandson.

John Henry: john@geolmaps.com

The Great Bindon Landslide: towards a modern model?

Online talk, September 2022

Richard Edmonds

The Great Bindon Landslide of 1839 is one of the most famous and most celebrated landslides in the world and yet, to date there has been no modern model to explain how it formed. Richard Edmonds has looked at evidence, old and new, to come up with a fresh interpretation of the event.

The tumultuous events that occurred at Bindon on Christmas Eve, Christmas Day and Boxing Day in 1839 involved 16 acres of land that slipped seaward, creating Goat Island, isolated from the cliff by a yawning chasm. The movement also created an enormous toe heave that pushed up the seabed well offshore. The landslide was so great a spectacle that even Queen Victoria came to view it from her yacht. One gentleman from Honiton, was so overwhelmed by the scene that he had to be taken to his sick bed and was *'only recovered with some great difficulty'*! It was truly a natural phenomenon and must have influenced thinking about Catastrophism over Uniformitarianism: a debate that was currently well underway. Today we know that it was actually quite a small landslide but, like the Great Storm of 1824, it must have been seen locally as a catastrophic event.

The *Ten Plates* (1840) authored by William Conybeare with maps and sections by William Dawson, illustrations by Dawson and Mary Buckland and 'revised' by William Buckland, provided the first attempt to understand what had happened. It was one of the earliest papers ever written on landslides.

Title page from *Ten Plates*

Since then, numerous models for what happened at Bindon have been put forward, but none have been truly satisfactory. The latest work on the subject, (Gallois 2010) suggests that Conybeare, Dawson and Buckland were in fact 'about right first time'.

Part of the problem today is that the area has become greatly overgrown, to the point that large parts are now totally inaccessible. This makes the early illustrations in the *Ten Plates*, and the photographs which followed a few decades

later, very valuable – along with the eye-witness accounts of the time. John Pitts, in his 1981 PhD, brought all of these together, along with the first modern map of the disrupted area, but even he struggled with access in some parts of the complex. As a result, the glass plate images by Charles Grover and others, unattributed, have proved essential in unlocking the story. Fortunately, this collection is now safeguarded by Lyme Regis Museum.

William Dawson was a surveyor based in Exeter and his map is quite remarkable. Not only did he recognise the need to start with a map, he also appreciated that an oblique view of the complex would add to the visualisation of the topography.

William Dawson's plan and sections of the landslide

In addition, Dawson realised the importance of cross sections and produced a number through the Chasm, across Goat Island and down onto the beach with the spectacular toe heave. That work was modified to form a section in the *Ten Plates* paper in which Conybeare attempted to come up with a model to explain the observed landform.

William Conybeare's explanatory (composite) section through the landslide

This section has been cited many times with people assuming that it is a section straight through the complex, through the middle of Goat Island. However, after much pondering it became evident that the section does not fit anywhere on Dawson's map and could indeed be a composite

The Great Bindon Landslide

of a number of sections. Dawson only produced one section through the whole complex and it only skimmed the eastern edge of Goat Island with the rest being in Dowlands. By tending to conceal the fact that there were actually two major landslides involved in this event, this has had catastrophic consequences to modern interpretations. The first movement was at Dowlands, a pre-existing landslide that initially failed on Christmas Eve, and which unloaded a second slide at Bindon which failed a day later to form the Chasm and Goat Island. The evidence for this is provided by the contemporary accounts of labourer William Pritchard, who returned late to Dowland's cottages after celebrating Christmas Eve at Bindon Manor. He was woken by a *'splendid crack'* at three in the morning; Dowlands was moving, and it continued to move until the following evening when it unloaded *'a cape-like headland'* that was later to become Goat Island.

The advance of high-resolution aerial photography, LiDAR and bathymetry freely provided under the Strategic Monitoring Programme at the Plymouth Coastal Observatory, has made it possible to draw up a new map of the complex. Then, using the hedgerows, older illustrations and photographs, it has been possible to reconstruct the landscape to a reasonable starting point and sequence the events step by step, both in map and sectional form. Offsets of the old hedge lines suggest that Goat Island may have rotated in a clockwise direction, in plan form.

The two separate movements that contributed to the Great Bindon Landslide

The account of *'a sound like renting cloth'* is really useful; if Goat Island did fail as a hinge slip, the ground would tear open like a zip for a number of hours and the complex would have advanced progressively from east to west. The impossible pinnacles in Dawson's illustration could be explained by this listric, horizontal displacement, pushing slip bound blocks of the cliff seaward. Furthermore, the pinnacles are literally that; this work has highlighted the importance of a dry valley running through what is now the slip and the back of the pinnacles could indeed be the steep southern slope of that valley.

The modern sections have been produced as a sequence that is complemented by the eye-witness accounts. This

Richard Edmonds

sequence provides vectors of movement that can be seen in the old photographs and identifies features such as the original toe heave on the beach today. The historic images and accounts provide the assurance needed to make such interpretations; indeed, look at the images long enough and it suddenly becomes apparent what was going on. This is particularly helpful as it takes weeks if not months to start to get a feel for the landslide and the historic evidence gives both clues and confirmation to interpretation of what may have gone on. Without them, this work would have been even harder—perhaps even impossible.

Sections showing a modern interpretation of the movement of the blocks

William Dawson's line drawing looking west. The toe heave is spectacular and simple to explain, just think of a bulldozer pushing a pile of earth. The pinnacles are much more problematic but, as Goat Island failed in response to the movement of Dowlands, on its eastern side, then it could have rotated as a hinge slip, thrusting sheared blocks of rock seaward. And as there is a dry valley running through the complex, the back of the pinnacles could be that valley, accounting for the otherwise impossible and unlikely form.

Images of 'Ten Plates', courtesy Lyme Regis Museum; modern interpretation by the author.

Richard Edmonds
jurassicrichard@gmail.com

Unlocking Lapworth's Legacy

Online talk, October 2022

Rachel Brown

It was my pleasure to speak with HOGG for the first time last October about the archive of Charles Lapworth (1842-1920), held by the Lapworth Museum of Geology. For those not familiar with the Museum, it is part of the School of Geography, Earth and Environmental Sciences at the University of Birmingham. As well as rocks, fossils and minerals, the Museum holds an extensive archive, mostly made up of collections from former heads of the Geology department. Charles Lapworth's archive is the oldest and largest part of the collection. Lapworth became the first Professor of Geology at Mason College (the University's predecessor) in 1881, and his archive gives a fantastic insight into many aspects of his research, teaching and personal life. Thanks to funding from Archives Revealed, in August 2021 the Museum began an 18-month project to catalogue and promote this fascinating collection.

Early life and career

Charles Lapworth was born on 20th September 1842 in Faringdon, Oxfordshire (Berkshire at the time), and grew up in nearby Buckland where his father worked as an agricultural labourer. Charles did not follow in his father's farming footsteps; in 1862 he attended Culham College, a teacher training school near Oxford. His student record, a copy of which was made by Lapworth's granddaughter and kept with his archive, tells us he had a bass, or deep, voice, a nugget of information about a physical characteristic which we would

not otherwise have known. He left the College at the end of 1863 to take up a post as Headteacher at the Episcopal Church School, Galashiels, Scotland, where he taught for 11 years. He was particularly interested in art and English, and according to an article published in the *Geological Magazine*, he took the job in Galashiels to be in the borderlands of Sir Walter Scott, the Scottish novelist, poet and playwright.

Portrait of Charles Lapworth, (late 19th century-early 20th century) Ref. CL/9/L/1

In the mid-late 1860s, Lapworth began to explore his surroundings and study the geology of the Scottish borders. He started to discover fossils, namely graptolites, in areas where the Geological Survey had said there weren't any. During this time, geologists were arguing over the boundaries of the Cambrian and Silurian systems. After years of

meticulous research and mapping, in 1879 Lapworth proposed a new geological time period, the Ordovician, which sat between the two contested eras and acted as a compromise in the Cambro-Silurian controversy. However, it was not readily accepted, not least by the Geological Survey who were reluctant to accept new theories by a then unknown geologist. There are many discussions about this in Lapworth's correspondence, and this quote nicely illustrates John E. Marr's thoughts on the matter:

I want Hughes [presumably Thomas McKenny Hughes]...to settle the Cambro-Silurian controversy over a bottle of port. I think Hughes might accept Ordovician with a little pressure, if the D.G. [Director General of the Geological Survey, Archibald Geikie] would only do the same. I am sick of the whole business.

John Marr to Lapworth, 22 November 1885, CL/1/MAR/3

Section from Lapworth's *Southern Uplands notebook*, 1869

Ref CL/2/1/10

In 1886 the Ordovician was accepted by the Geological Society of London, with John Hopkinson writing to Lapworth, 'We've carried Ordovician today by 5 to 1...and about as many did not vote at all. It is the smallest meeting we have had' (Ref. CL/1/HOP/3). Does the fact that only half of the Society's council voted on the matter mean that they did not agree with Lapworth's theories, or perhaps that they didn't think it was of much importance?

Family life

Lapworth's time in the Scottish borders was also significant to him personally as it was here that he met his wife, Janet Sanderson, the daughter of another local schoolteacher.

Charles Lapworth with his wife Janet in their garden, early 20th century

Ref. CL/9/M/2

Unlocking Lapworth's Legacy

Rachel Brown

Whilst Janet does not feature in the archive much, there are a couple of letters between the couple from when Charles visited Switzerland in 1893. These show an informal side to them both, with Charles addressing Janet as 'Dearest Birdie', and her addressing him as 'Dear Hubby'.

The couple married in 1869 and had five children together between 1871 and 1882, but sadly the first-born, Ernest, died at just two weeks old and the last-born, Walter Sanderson, died before his second birthday. In the archive there are a couple of condolence letters on the death of their youngest child in 1884.

I think the love of little children here makes many hard things seem plain and when they are gone, it may be, that we are linked through them to the "things unseen".

M.C. Hughes to Lapworth, 9 April 1884, CL/1/LAL/2

Teaching at Mason College

After Lapworth's pioneering research in southern Scotland, in 1881 he became the first Professor of Geology at the newly established Mason College, the forerunner to the University of Birmingham which was founded in 1900.

His archive contains various teaching records such as attendance registers, prospectuses, visual aids, lecture notes and student notebooks. Unlike some educational institutions, women were always able to attend classes at Mason College, and in fact all of the student notebooks in Lapworth's archive were made by women. Most were by a woman called Bertha Leslie between 1886 and 1889, and she'd inscribed them with an address of 'Moor Green Hall'. After searching the 1881 census, I found that she was actually a governess for the Chamberlain family at Moor Green Hall, near Highbury Park in Birmingham. Perhaps she was taking the geology classes in order to pass on the knowledge to her pupils? Leslie carried on her career in education and eventually moved to Cornwall; her notebooks were actually found in a school cupboard in Redruth before being passed on to the Museum!

Colourful geological map drawn by Bertha Leslie, a student of Lapworth's, c1886
Ref. CL/4/3/17

After over 30 years of teaching, Lapworth retired in 1913 at the age of 71. A fund was set up to buy him a leaving present

(an Angelus player piano) and alongside monetary donations, former students wrote some really lovely letters about Lapworth's teaching and the impact he had on them.

His lectures studded with touches of humour, flashes of deep scientific import, and sometimes strains of poetical fancy colouring the grey summits of facts and figures...have added in no small measure to the joy and interest of my life. To me he was always the ideal of the teacher and man of science.

W. Howard Jevons to William Boulton, Lapworth's successor in the Chair of Geology, 3 November 1913, CL/4/15/4

Highlands Controversy and illness

Not one to shy away from a geological controversy, Lapworth's first research project after becoming a Professor at Mason College was in the north-west Highlands of Scotland, an area of contention amongst geologists. The Geological Survey held firm to Roderick Murchison's view that there was a straightforward ascending succession to the Highlands, despite mounting research opposing this. Lapworth visited Durness and Eriboll in 1882 and 1883 and proposed that there was no chronological sequence discernible in the mountains, as the ground had been subject to considerable folding and crushing.

Sketch of Loch Eriboll by Charles Lapworth, 1882-1883

Ref. CL/2/3/6

The following year, the Survey sent two of its own surveyors, Ben Peach and John Horne, to settle the controversy once and for all. Peach and Horne came to a similar conclusion to Lapworth, and so the Survey was forced to concede defeat. The Director of the Survey, Archibald Geikie, chose to publish these findings in the magazine *Nature* rather than in an official Survey publication, and did not credit any other geologists who had already arrived at these conclusions. Correspondence between Peach and Lapworth show that there were no hard feelings between the two men despite the Survey's behaviour, with Peach acknowledging Lapworth's findings had been mostly correct.

By you we have been anticipated as I shall make it distinctly apparent in anything I have to write on the matter. In some of the details we apparently differ but in the main we are at one.

Ben Peach to Lapworth, 4 January 1885, CL/1/PEA/2

Unlocking Lapworth's Legacy

Rachel Brown

On his return to Birmingham in 1883, Lapworth experienced a physical and mental illness and it's thought that this was, at least in part, brought on by the strenuous fieldwork and the stress of opposing the Geological Survey on the Highlands Controversy. Mason College gave Lapworth three months of paid leave to aid his recovery, and employed an assistant to cover his duties. It's warming to see the support and kind words Lapworth received from his friends and colleagues. One in particular, Henry Alleyne Nicholson, draws on his own experience to empathise with Lapworth.

I am very sorry indeed to hear that you have been ill. I am afraid I am hardly the man to pitch into you for overworking yourself but I do hope you will take a warning in time and will follow my example in trying to take a long rest. I am beginning to discover, by painful experience, how very slow and disheartening a process it is to build up and restore an exhausted nervous system.

Henry A. Nicholson to Lapworth, 25 August 1883, CL/1/NIA/26

Thanks to a doctor's note written in 1904 referring to Lapworth's 'severe nervous breakdown', we know that, unfortunately, he continued to have issues with his health for decades to come.

Letter from George H. Morley, Secretary at Mason College, to Charles Lapworth, confirming the College will employ an assistant in his absence, 3 October 1883
Ref. CL/1/UOB/3/2

Women in geology

Lapworth's archive not only sheds light on him, but also his friends and colleagues which included a number of female geologists. There is a large amount of correspondence between Lapworth and Maria Ogilvie Gordon, who did a lot of research in the Dolomites and shares her experience of travelling through Europe.

...As I am touring alone, I had already previously arranged with men at different villages to come and carry my "Rucksack" and fossils...It is by no means easy to be a lady geologist in Bavaria! The people think I am a poor mad young thing and treat me almost with patronising kindness.

Maria Ogilvie to Lapworth, 27 May 1892, CL/1/OGI/16

Lapworth collaborated with Gertrude Elles and Ethel Wood [later Shakespear] on a *Monograph of British Graptolites* in the early 1900s. On being asked to work on the publication, Elles replied to Lapworth saying she would 'place herself entirely in [his] hands', which is quite a subservient statement. It seems Lapworth was uncomfortable with this, as in his draft reply he wrote,

I don't wish you to place yourself in my hands...I want you to do exactly what will make your mind easiest and happiest.

1899, CL/1/MON/3-4

Lapworth and students, including his daughter Edith and Ethel Wood, on a field trip in Worcestershire, Jun 1897
Ref. CL/9/B/17

Accessing the archive

It is now easier than ever to search the collection using the online catalogue at lapwortharchive.bham.ac.uk. Archive visits may be booked by emailing

lapworth@contacts.bham.ac.uk.

Tour groups are often brought into the archive to view original documents and an online version of an exhibition exploring Lapworth's life and archive should be available soon on the Museum's 3D modelling platform:

www.sketchfab.com/LapworthMuseum

Throughout the project I wrote blog posts charting our progress and highlighting various documents; if you'd like to catch up on these you can do so by visiting our WordPress site: lapworthmuseum.wordpress.com.

It was a real pleasure getting to know Charles Lapworth through his archive during the cataloguing project, which was completed in January 2023. I'm sure there are many more stories in the collection left to uncover and I hope the archive will be of interest and value to many people for years to come.

All images are reproduced courtesy of the Lapworth Museum.

Rachel Brown
rachb474@hotmail.com

Rachel is a former Project Archivist at the Lapworth Museum of Geology.

Arthur Young and the first geological maps of Norfolk and Suffolk

Online talk, February 2023

Peter Riches

Peter Riches' research has led him to conclude that the soil maps produced by Arthur Young at the turn of the nineteenth century might legitimately be considered to be the earliest geological maps of Norfolk and Suffolk.

Modern geological maps are characterized by the use of coloured areas to represent the distribution of geological units. This method of representation, rather than just marking mineral or rock locations on maps, was first adopted in Germany and France in the second half of the eighteenth century¹. This new visual language for representing geological information was adopted much later in Britain, notably by William Smith in his map *A Delineation of the Strata in England and Wales...* (1815)². This map by Smith and his county maps of Norfolk and Suffolk published in 1819 are generally considered to be the first geological maps covering these counties. However, from 1794 the Board of Agriculture published coloured soil maps in some of their reports on the agriculture of each county³. Arthur Young was responsible for the reports and maps of Suffolk (Figure 1, 1794) and Norfolk (Figure 2, 1804).

Figure 1 Young's soil map of Suffolk first published 1794.

Author's collection.

Arthur Young (Fig. 3, 1741 – 1820) lived most of his life in his family's ancestral home and farm in Suffolk at Bradfield Combust, near Bury St Edmunds. Young soon established a name for himself as an authority on the practice of agriculture and its improvement. He enjoyed travel and made several extensive tours of England, Ireland and France. His written work is characterized by the use of quantification in his observations, the comparison of agricultural systems and a desire to test ideas through experimentation. In 1793 he was appointed as Secretary of the newly-formed Board of Agriculture (effectively, he was the Board's Chief Executive). He remained in this job until his death.

Lister was probably the first to suggest that colour be used on maps to show the distribution of soils in 1684⁴. Nearly a

Figure 2 Young's soil map of Norfolk first published 1804.

Author's collection.

hundred years later in 1771⁵, Young echoed Lister's suggestion by writing that he would rejoice 'to see one [soil map] which distinguished the nature of the soil, by different colours' and he was possibly the first in Britain to adopt the new visual language where blocks of colour on a map are used to illustrate the lateral extent of geological elements. His first published soil map was of France in 1792⁶ and it seems likely that Young drew up his soil map of Suffolk (his home county) sometime before 1787 although it was not published until 1794⁷. Although the first two editions of the Norfolk report (by Nathaniel Kent) lacked a soil map, Young's coloured soil map of Norfolk was published in the third edition⁸.

Unlike much of Britain's geology, that of Norfolk and Suffolk is dominated by superficial deposits or 'Drift' and, as Smith often found, mapping the lithological boundaries and extent of different units can be problematic. This is because the lateral extent and thickness of different litho-

Figure 3 Arthur Young.

©The Trustees of the British Museum

logies can change gradually and frequently. These deposits were formed from glacial, fluvial, marine and wind action over the last million years and are, unusually, as much as 60 metres thick. The Chalk outcrops on the western margins of the two counties. Extensive marine shelly sands of Plio-Pleistocene age (also called Crag) outcrop in the area next to the coast in southeast Suffolk. The central parts of Suffolk and Norfolk are covered by the extensive deposit of the glacial till ('Boulder Clay') of the Lowestoft Formation. In Suffolk, the Lowestoft Formation till outcrop approximates to the area called 'heavy loam' in Young's Suffolk map (Figure 1) and the western half of the large area of 'various loams' in his Norfolk map (Figure 2).

A comparison of Young's map of Suffolk with William Smith's 1815 *Delineation of the Strata of England and Wales...* (See Figure 4) shows striking similarities. However, a notable difference would appear to be that Smith's map shows Chalk (in green) outcropping on the west side partially covered by sand (in light brown) whereas only sand is shown in the same area on Young's map. This is not a substantive difference but only one of emphasis.

Figure 4. Young's Suffolk soil map boundaries (shown in blue) overlaid on an extract of William Smith's 1815 *A Delineation of the Strata of England and Wales...* (reproduced by permission of the Geological Society of London).

There are significant differences in the shape of the coast and rivers that form the county's boundaries between the two maps which preclude a precise overlay.

In Young's report he described an understratum of perfect, uninterrupted chalk at various depths below the sands of western Suffolk, whereas on Smith's map, the western boundary of the sand on the Chalk is not defined by a line, but by the light brown colouring fading out gradually (the position of this varies from copy to copy of the map). The dark brown area on the map represents Smith's 'Clay or brickearth' and agrees with Young's area of 'strong loam'. Young recognized that the strong loams lay on a 'clay-marl bottom', i.e., the till of the Lowestoft Formation. The lighter brown coloured area on either side of the 'Clay with brickearth' represents Smith's 'great sand with crag' and, except in the far west of the county, is in accordance with the sand shown on Young's map. Young (in his 1794 Suffolk report) and Smith (in his 1816 *Strata Identified by Organized Fossils*) describe similar distributions for the crag sands in

southeast Suffolk. There are broad similarities between Young and Smith's maps of Norfolk, but these are not as great as in their maps of Suffolk. The western boundary of Young's area of 'various loams' is very similar to the western boundary of Smith's 'Clay with brickearth' and it represents the edge of the Lowestoft formation till.

As William Smith would have had ready access to Young's maps when making his maps, the similarities between their maps suggest that, as Thomas Sheppard states (in his important memoir on Smith), there can be little doubt that Smith used Young's maps when making his own map⁹.

The British Geological Survey and its predecessors have generated two types of geological map: solid geology and superficial geology or 'Drift'. Both of Young's Norfolk and Suffolk maps and, to a large extent, the part of Smith's map that covers Norfolk and Suffolk have mapped superficial sediments rather than solid geology. The close similarity between the two maps of Suffolk and to a lesser extent that of Norfolk indicates that if Smith's map is geological then perhaps we can reasonably claim that Young's maps are also geological. Indeed, the influential early nineteenth century geologists Conybeare and Phillips considered that the Board of Agriculture 'produced the earliest geological maps of any part of England' and H B Woodward, who spent many years mapping Norfolk for the Geological Survey, considered Young's Norfolk soil map to be 'in reality a Drift map'¹⁰.

¹ Taylor, K.L., 1985. 'Early geoscience mapping, 1700-1830.' *Proceedings of the Geoscience Information Society*, 15, pp.15-49.

² William Smith produced his first, but unpublished, geological map of the area around Bath in 1799

³ From a geological perspective, John Farey's 1811 report on Derbyshire is the most notable of these because it contained the first published geological map and description based on the ideas of William Smith

⁴ Lister, M., 1684. 'An Ingenious Proposal for a New Sort of Maps of Countries,...' *Philosophical Transactions*, Vol 14 p.739-746

⁵ Young, A. 1771. *The Farmer's Letters to the People of England* 3rd ed., Vol 1 p.87.

⁶ Young, A., 1792. *Travels during the years 1787, 1788 and 1789 ... the Kingdom of France.*

⁷ Young, A. 1794. *General View of the Agriculture of the County of Suffolk.*

⁸ Young, A. 1804. *General View of the Agriculture of the County of Norfolk.*

⁹ Sheppard, T., 1918. 'William Smith: his maps and memoirs.' *Proceedings of the Yorkshire Geological Society*. v.19, p.101

¹⁰ Conybeare, W.D. & Phillips, W. 1822. *Outlines of the Geology of England and Wales*. p.xlv; Woodward, H.B., 1912. *The geology of soils and substrata, with special reference to agriculture, estates, and sanitation*. p.25.

George Cumberland: Farming – Family – Fossils. Aspects of a Somerset life in letters 1800-35

K. Jane Evans

Somerset Archaeological and Natural History Society 2022
A4 softback. 150 pp, including a comprehensive index and 67 illustrations in colour and black and white, with 23 of Cumberland's own work.

Copies are available, priced at £15, from SANHS website at <https://sanhs.org/product/george-cumberland-farming-family-fossils-by-k-jane-evans/>

George Cumberland (1754-1848) was a polymath – an accomplished watercolourist, prolific writer, experimental printmaker, inventor, musician and pioneer geologist. He is today perhaps best remembered for his association with William Blake who, like him, was both a poet and artist.

In this recently published book Jane Evans brings to light various aspects of Cumberland's life based on her many years of meticulous research and painstaking review of several thousand of Cumberland's letters now preserved at the British Library.

The initial part of this book focuses on Cumberland's attempts at farming in the Mendips, his years of residence at Weston super Mare (where he first developed his interest in geology), and his subsequent move to Bristol where he was one of the earliest members of the Bristol School of artists. Later chapters deal with Cumberland's interest in geology and his family relationships.

It is the chapter on Cumberland the geologist that will perhaps most fascinate the HOGG Membership. This chapter, which occupies 22 pages, includes much previously unpublished information on Cumberland's geological doings, as well as reproductions of many of his watercolours of geological subjects and his pioneering lithographs of fossils.

Cumberland's interest in geology began with collecting mineral specimens, but in time he became increasingly interested in fossils, particularly crinoids which were the subject of his most important publication *Reliquiae Conservatae* (1826). Cumberland also contributed several papers on crinoids as well as on the geology of the Bristol District to the Transactions of the Geological Society of London, and published numerous other geology-related articles in various scientific journals and local newspapers.

One of the things that is most striking on reading this account of Cumberland's life is the extent of his correspondence with other early geologists including the Reverends Joseph Townsend and Benjamin Richardson,

Etheldred Benett, Margaret Philpot, Mary Anning and Gideon Mantell (much of this correspondence being related to the purchase and exchange of geological specimens). In researching and documenting this correspondence Jane Evans reveals aspects of Cumberland's character, his daily life, and his network of acquaintances, thereby illuminating the man behind the dry science. Here then is Cumberland in his own words and those of his family.

Cumberland's pioneering geological studies did not enjoy the same reception as that of other contemporaries such as the similarly Bristol-based J.S. Miller (author of *A Natural History of the Crinoidea* (1821)). This lack of scientific recognition may be due in part to the fact that Cumberland lacked an eminent patron. Miller in contrast enjoyed the patronage of Conybeare, Buckland and Sedgwick, and had the additional benefit of prominence in his role as curator of the Bristol Institution.

Cumberland's last geological publication (*Some Account of the Order in which Fossil Saurians were Discovered*) appeared in 1829, and in 1836 he put up for sale his collection of over 7000 British Fossils (some of which still survive in the Manchester Museum).

In later years Cumberland's *Reliquiae Conservatae* was deliberately overlooked by Thomas Austin Sr. and Thomas Austin Jr. who in their *Monograph on Recent and Fossil Crinoidea* (1843-1849) misleadingly remarked that "we do not possess a single work, with the exception of Miller's, that is devoted entirely to the subject [of Crinoidea]".

While Cumberland may not have enjoyed the scientific standing of other contemporary workers in the field, his work on crinoids still has currency in that he was the first person to figure and describe *Mitra (Acentrotremites) elliptica* and he was the first to illustrate *Poteriocrinus longidactylus*. His chalk lithographs of fossils, some of which were separately published, remain significant as being amongst the earliest and most important thus produced.

Jane Evans' fascinating book on Cumberland is thoroughly researched, beautifully written, and includes extensive illustrations and endnotes. It is printed on high quality gloss paper and represents exceptional value at £15. I recommend it to the HOGG Membership and to anyone with an interest in the history of geology.

Christopher Toland
christophertoland@hotmail.com

Making it Mine; Sir Arthur Russell and his Mineral Collection

Roy Starkey

British Mineralogy Publications 2022 £50.00 (incl. p&rp in UK)
ISBN 978-0-9930182-4-4 426pp

This large ambitious book has two subjects: the talented and obsessive collector, and his legacy – the Sir Arthur Russell Collection of British Minerals, now in the Natural History Museum.

The Russell Collection is ‘widely regarded as the most magnificent and comprehensive private collection of British Isles minerals ever made’ says NHM’s principal curator, Mike Rumsey. It consists of approximately 14,000 specimens, about half personally collected, the rest acquired historic collections. Its value as a reference collection lies in Russell’s careful documentation of the specific mines and localities from which his minerals had been collected.

This is no conventional biography as Sir Arthur’s life (1878-1964) was so entwined with his collection. The author achieves clarity by carefully disentangling the two strands. It was an odd life. His family had earned wealth and title through generations of service to the East India Company, eventually investing in railways and land, and spending lavishly on a big house and lifestyle.

By Arthur Russell’s time, this period was drawing to a close. He did not fit in at Eton or Cambridge and never completed his formal education. However, inheriting an interest in mineral collecting from his mother and grandmother, he became absorbed in the science of mineralogy. Family contacts with the owners of mines and quarries in the West Country gave him access to remarkable collecting and learning opportunities and he became a self-educated expert. In 1915 he was invalided out of the WW1 Red Cross ambulance service and, unable to re-enlist, he was at a loss until an influential relative linked his mineralogical expertise to the needs of the Ministry of Munitions. As a mines inspector he visited metalliferous mines throughout the British Isles, expanding his knowledge and developing a network of contacts. After the war, death duties left the Russells property rich but cash poor. By the Depression, Russell was living in two, later three, rooms of Swallowfields, a 30-odd room Berkshire mansion that was decaying around him. But it did give him space for his minerals.

Having introduced the family and the development of Swallowfields, the biographical aspect of the book truly begins in Chapter 4. The story is well told, supported by photographs and interviews with his surviving sons and grandsons.

A somewhat appendix-like chapter 5, ‘Goniometry and Crystal Drawing’, introduces Russell’s meticulous analytical

approach, but chapters 6 to 8 revert to biography, treating his professional life; the Mineralogical Society, consultancy work, and the attempted revival of New Consols Mine.

Chapter 9 outlines the building of Russell’s collection and describes his work rooms at Swallowfields, with chapter 10 focusing on his field collecting by regions. Chapter 11 discusses and gives much interesting information on the numerous old collections he acquired. His correspondence and careful records reveal his courtesy and dogged persistence. Although generally ultimately successful, negotiations were sometimes protracted, but what is surprising is the relatively low values he paid, even allowing for inflation, both for individual specimens and whole collections. Russell was ahead of his time in appreciating these collections, which often represented localities that have since been worked out, flooded or built over. Images of the original collectors and photographs of the spectacular minerals add to the great interest of this chapter.

Russell was also a dealer, and his friendships with other successful dealers as well as colleagues and personal contacts in the mining industry, academia and museums are covered in chapters 12 and 13.

Towards the end of his life, concerned with his legacy, Russell negotiated with both the NHM and Oxford University Museum of Natural History, secretly committing to both, but eventually settling for the NHM, his initial choice. This saga and the immense task, after Russell’s death, of moving the collection to London and subsequently documenting it, are described in chapters 14 and 15.

Chapters 16 and 17, which give us some stunning illustrations of the choicest parts of the collection, comprise almost a third of the book and the author’s final two chapters deal with Russell’s unpublished work and his archive.

A closing chapter, by Mike Rumsey, discusses the research value and enduring legacy of the Russell collection. For example, a previously unknown mineral, Kernowite, collected by Phillip Rashleigh (1729-1811) and acquired by Russell in 1923 was discovered by NHM curators using the latest analytical tools.

With extensive footnotes and informative captions, the book also has an exhaustive reference list and several useful appendices. The index is excellent, although it does miss some people and places found only in footnotes.

The author, president of The Russell Society, has produced a well-researched and beautifully illustrated reference work in association with the NHM. *Making it Mine* is for the keen mineral collector and mineralogist, and for the historian interested in the cultural aspects of mineral collecting and trading.

John Henry: john@geolmaps.com

A Story in Stone: The Geology of the Oxford University Museum of Natural History

Nina Morgan and Philip Powell

Geologica Press 2022
<https://www.gravestonegeology.uk>

£18.00
 160pp

When Imperial College's Professor Herbert Read famously suggested in 1940 that 'the best geologist is he who has seen the most rocks' he made explicit an idea that had been given concrete form 80 years earlier in the building of Oxford's new Museum.

The builders of this grand neo-Gothic edifice not only roofed it with the most up-to-date plate glass and ironwork structure to ensure a well-lit exhibition space—it was less than ten years since the great Crystal Palace had been erected in Hyde Park—but they also incorporated as many different types of rock as they could in the supporting walls. Now known as the Oxford University Museum of Natural History (OUMNH), this wonderful cathedral of science should be on the itinerary of all visitors to Oxford, and especially those with a geological bent. The curated exhibits are all of the very highest quality, but also the building itself is, as the authors Nina Morgan and Philip Powell suggest, truly *A Story in Stone*.

The book explains how the polymathic John Phillips (1800-1874), nephew of William Smith and newly appointed Professor of Geology at the university, was one of the driving forces behind the establishment of the museum, which

he saw primarily as a resource for the teaching of science—and most especially, geology. It was at Phillips' suggestion that the decoration and even the structure of the building itself should be made to play their part in this educational endeavour. In addition to gifts of money, wealthy landowners were encouraged to contribute, from their country estates,

specimens of rock to be made into decorative pillars. Also no fewer than thirteen different types of stone were used in the façade of the building, and even the floors display a more than usual variety of colours and textures.

To enable his students and other visitors to gain all they could from this rich geological display, in 1863 Phillips produced a pamphlet describing the stone shafts and the capitals they supported. This new book is a worthy modern successor to Phillips' work. Each column is described in detail, with notes about provenance and mineralogical composition. All the entries are supported with superb photographs, both of the whole shaft and, most

usefully, close-ups of the rock itself. The written descriptions are clear and accessible to anyone with the merest interest in the subject, and the book ends with a useful glossary and stratigraphic table.

So, in conclusion, not only should visitors to Oxford be sure to include the museum in their itinerary, but they should do so with this excellent book in hand! And for those unable to see the building for themselves, the beautiful photographs in this well-designed volume provide an excellent proxy.

Peter Lincoln
peter.c.lincoln@gmail.com

HOGG Conference & Field Meeting—Ireland 2023

Aspects of the history and progress of geology in Ireland 15-18 August 2023

This meeting will explore the history of geology in Ireland from the 18th to the mid-20th century, encompassing aspects that advanced the understanding of geology both within Ireland and beyond its shores. The conference venue is Trinity College Dublin Museum Building - which is itself a monument to geology!

Low conference fee: €17 (payable on arrival)

Call for presentations:
 Send proposals (250 words) by 1 June to Patrick Wyse Jackson at wysjcknp@tcd.ie

The programme (subject to change):

Day 1: (All day) Conference presentations at Trinity College Dublin and tour of TCD Museum building

Day 2: (am) Tour of Geological Museum, TCD; visit to Richard Griffith's Dublin residence; (pm) Memorialising Irish geologists - visit to tombs and burial places in a Dublin cemetery

Day 3: (am) Killiney Beach - Robert Mallet and the beginning of scientific seismology + the Ailsa Craig connection; (pm) Geological Survey of Ireland

Day 4: (am) National Museum of Ireland visit (& optional extension viewing 'Down to Earth - Exploring Ireland's Geology' exhibition)

For further details and to reserve your place, visit:

<https://tinyurl.com/2p9xfuua>

Enquiries to: duncan.hawley.hogg@gmail.com

The Geological Society's Map—in person at last!

9 March 2023

John Henry

The geological maps of England and Wales of George Bellas Greenough (1778-1855)—all three editions—were the subject and main attraction of the Geological Society's first evening meeting since the pandemic ended. It was hosted by the Library and the Society as a fee-paying event, and as a consequence, it perhaps attracted a wider audience than a HOGG meeting would have. Even in the absence of refreshments, this, the first LIVE event in three years, was a warm and convivial meeting and there was a certain delight in simply being able to get together.

An appropriately clad Duncan Hawley explains the intricacies of the different editions of the map.

The Greenough maps were actually publications of the Geological Society, although, as GBG financed them, his name featured prominently on the first two editions. The three maps were spread beside each other so that the developing interpretation and portrayal of the geology, from 1820 to 1865, could be compared and appreciated. HOGG's acting chairperson, Duncan Hawley, impressively attired in his self-made GBG map pullover, was

finally able to give a presentation originally intended for the 2020 HOGG conference to celebrate the bicentenary of the first edition. Although the conference papers were all eventually given in a Zoom meeting in 2021, the 'practical presentation' was then still not possible.

Duncan set the scene with some background information. GBG had been destined for the law, and seriously considered becoming an architect, before deciding to be a gentleman natural philosopher. Whatever his field of endeavour, his ambition was to be the best practitioner of it. Ergo, he was not just a founder of the Geological Society but also its first president. And it was he who, in 1808, initiated, and then coordinated, its first project—a geological map of England and Wales.

GBG was obsessed with detail and getting things right. This caused considerable delay as he compiled and edited the contributions of numerous Society members to produce the map. The first draft was ready in 1812, but then the intended base map was dropped. Aaron Arrowsmith's (1750-1823), rendition of the country's topography, although acknowledged as the best available at the time, was just not good enough for GBG, who insisted that it must be re-drawn with a consistent angle of illumination. This required an expensive new engraving, so GBG brought it in-house for talented GS employee Thomas Webster (1772-1844) to complete. As information flowed in, details kept changing and were re-drawn*. The publication date on the map is 1 Nov. 1819, but the map was not actually issued until 1 May

1820. Similarly, the second edition of 1839 was issued in 1840. The third edition, of 1865, was beyond GBG's influence.

From the outset, there were claims that GBG's map plagiarised William Smith's 1815 work. But detail of linework, introduction of new units, and obviously new work in the difficult metamorphic and igneous terrains where Smith had not worked contradicted the charge.

The second edition introduced more units and new vocabulary. It also experimented successfully with colour theory and the combination of engraved patterns with colour, while retaining the muted colours favoured in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. The third edition was not issued until ten years after GBG's death. It had the Geological Society's name in the title, and William Smith was acknowledged as a source, with others. The colours were bright in keeping with later Victorian taste. A particularly interesting supporting document was discovered recently by Society archivist, Caroline Lam. It was the draft for the title block of the third edition prepared by John Phillips, then president of the GS. He was also the devoted nephew of William Smith, and was clearly putting right a perceived wrong. Also displayed were several manuscript source maps provided by the Society's Members (and later Fellows) and used in GBG's compilation.

The Geological Society's Map in the Geological Society's Library. (Spot the rhinoceros!)

Thanks to Caroline Lam and Library staff Michael McKimm and Paul Johnson who supported the meeting, and to Duncan for his well-informed and enthusiastic presentation. It was a most enjoyable and interesting evening.

* GBG may not have realised that he was in a race, but his perfectionism presented quite an opportunity to map-maker John Cary for whom Arrowsmith had once worked as a surveyor. Cary would doubtless have heard that GBG had cancelled the contract with Arrowsmith. It is the writer's opinion that, appreciating how long the re-engraving would take, Cary spotted an opportunity. William Smith tells us that 'The end of 1812 brought me a proposal from Mr. Cary to publish my Map of the Strata. Terms were soon settled, and the work commenced with the beginning of January 1813' (Phillips 1844, pp.70-71)

John Henry
john@geomaps.com

The origin and influence of Conybeare & Phillips’ *Outlines of the Geology of England and Wales*

2022 was the bicentenary of one of the most influential books in the early period of English geology. The title page of this ‘classic’ of British geological literature, affectionately known as ‘Conybeare-and-Phillips’, sets out clearly what the reader might expect to find within.

Extract from title page

Public domain

The origin

The origin of Conybeare and Phillips’ *Outlines* lies with the publisher and bookseller **William Phillips** (1775–1828), whose enthusiasm for the emerging sciences of the enlightenment, particularly crystallography, chemistry and mineralogy, had led to him becoming one of the founding members of the Geological Society in 1807. Phillips’ interests also caused him to self-publish a number of early scientific books, beginning in 1815 with *An Outline of Mineralogy and Geology, Intended for the use of those who may desire to become Acquainted with the Elements of those Sciences; especially of Young Persons*. With his commercial eye set firmly on beginners (in both England and North America) eager for introductory instruction, his clear writing style proved popular, and in 1816 he issued a second edition, to which he added, *An Outline Of The Geology Of England And Wales, With A Map And Section Of The Strata*. The map was a miniature version of William Smith’s of 1815 (used with permission), and the 37-page addition gave guidance on its interpretation together with sketches and locations of the different strata.

In 1818 Phillips produced a new 237-page book: *A Selection of Facts from the Best Authorities Arranged so as to form An Outline...* of which, he told readers, ‘[a] very large proportion has been extracted from the highly interesting and valuable volumes of the Transactions of the Geological Society...’ It included a revised map and a copy of William Buckland’s *Order of the Superposition of the Strata of the British Islands*—a later version of this important stratigraphical table would also appear in the 1822 *Outlines*. The 1818 book provided descriptions of the strata and their regions, including notes on their fossil contents. It reflected the shift away from mineralogical descriptions towards accounts of stratigraphy and the interpretation of the geological history of the Earth.

The **Reverend William Daniel Conybeare** (1787–1857)

read Phillips’ book. While a student at Christ Church, Oxford, Conybeare had attended John Kidd’s extracurricular mineralogical classes alongside his brother John and William Buckland. He was a leading member of Oxford’s ‘geological club’, a group of enthusiasts who were keen to develop ties with George Greenough and the Geological Society, which Conybeare joined in 1811. Between 1807 and 1814 he visited many areas of England and Wales, latterly sending detailed accounts of his fieldwork to Greenough, who was busy compiling the Geological Society’s map (published in 1820). In 1819 Conybeare moved Brislington, near Bristol, from where he explored the geology of the south west region. Having read *A Selection of Facts...*, he wrote a long letter to Phillips pointing out errors and suggesting much additional information, as a result of which Phillips asked Conybeare to collaborate with him on an improved work. The outcome, published in 1822, was much longer and more detailed than Phillips’ previous books, so they settled on a new title that reflected the more comprehensive volume, viz. *Outlines of the Geology of England and Wales...* Recognising that Conybeare was the principal author of this new volume, Phillips was initially reluctant to have his name appear at all, writing, ‘Conybeare’s assistance has been gratuitous, for he has no other interest in the work than as having contributed to it.’

The authors

The book

Published in July 1822, *Outlines* was the first really systematic work on the geology of England and Wales. Conceived as an instructive manual as much as a description of the geological structure of the country, Phillips had it printed in small type, on thin paper and in a relatively lightweight binding—to be carried by readers as an ‘interesting companion on their travels’. Compact and content-dense, the high church cleric Conybeare compared it to a Breviary—that compendium of the divine office so essential to those in holy orders.

The stratigraphical focus of the book is made clear at the outset. The reader is informed that a key purpose of geology is ‘ascertaining the order in which the materials constituting the surface of our planet (for beyond this our observation cannot penetrate) are disposed.’ Knowledge of chemistry or mineralogy are but subordinate acquisitions.

The bicentenary of ‘Conybeare & Phillips’

Duncan Hawley

In the introduction, Conybeare explains the principles of grouping strata into Formations, based on beds identical in character, and proposes that Formations can be divided into five ‘Orders’, derived ‘by comparing several of those formations together, a resemblance of relations and an association in position...’.

Character.	Proposed names.	Wernerian names.	Other writers.
1. Formations (chiefly of sand & clay) above the chalk.	Superior order.	Newest floetz class	Tertiary class.
2. Comprising a. Chalk. b. sands & clays beneath the chalk c. calcareous free-stones (oolites), & argillaceous beds. d. New red sandstone, conglomerate & magnesian limestone.	Supermedial order.	Floetz class.	Secondary class.
3. Carboniferous rocks, comprising a. Coal-measures. b. Carboniferous limestone. c. Old red sandstone	Medial order.	Sometimes referred to the preceding sometimes to the succeeding class by writers of these schools; very often the coal-measures are referred to the former—the subjacent limestone and sandstone to the latter.	
4. Roofing slate, &c. &c.	Submedial order.	Transition class.	Intermediate class.
5. Mica slate. Gneiss. Granite, &c.	Inferior order.	Primitive class.	Primitive class.

Conybeare's proposed 'Orders' of formations

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Phillips later adopted this grouping for the 4th edition of his *Outlines of Mineralogy and geology intended principally for the use of Young Persons* (1826), writing: ‘This division seems at once natural and instructive.’ The nomenclature, i.e. Superior, Supermedial and Medial, was intended to supplant the old terms ‘Primary’ and ‘Secondary’, and although this was not ultimately successful, it did open up the way for revised names for groupings of rocks to be applied.

The 1822 *Outlines* volume was titled ‘Part I’ and it focused on those strata known to contain fossils. As indicated on the maps of Smith (1815) and Greenough (1820), the strata below the Carboniferous (including Old Red Sandstone) were imperfectly known and were thought to possess few, if any, organic remains. Thus, as Part I included only the upper three orders, a Part II was anticipated—but it never materialised.

The introduction is as instructive to the historian of geology today as it was to the reader of two hundred years ago. Conybeare claims: ‘It is not the business of the present work to propose theories, but to record facts’, yet he outlines the predominant theoretical ideas and issues of geology of that time. Noting that marine remains have been found at the loftiest summits, Conybeare states the problem ‘is to assign adequate causes’ for the changes of level in the ocean. There follows a discussion of the merits of the possible chemical and mechanical explanations. It is an erudite exposition of contemporary geological thought and practice, including critical appraisal: of the ‘ordinary operation of actual causes’

espoused by Hutton; of Werner’s attempts at theorising (described as ‘among the most unsuccessful and unphilosophical ever made’); of the merits of Smith’s and Greenough’s maps; and even of geology’s relation to religion. Conybeare organised the main text into three ‘Books’, one for each respective Order. Books I and II, describing the Superior and Supermedial, were sub-divided into chapters and sections that provided a systematic description of ordered strata and formations, detailing the chemical and external characters, mineral and fossil contents, and the disposition of each. Book III, treating the Medial or Carboniferous Order, took a different approach. The first chapter gave a general view of the formations, followed by three chapters of regional accounts of coal districts, in geographical arrangement from north to south, viz. ‘Grand Pennine Chain’, ‘Central’ and ‘Western’. Conybeare originated the term ‘Pennine Chain’, now ubiquitously used for the ‘backbone of England’. Conybeare and Phillips or *Outlines* is commonly cited as the original source of naming the Carboniferous Period, although in fact, the term was first used by Richard Kirwan (1799), and John Farey Snr (1807, 1811). Similarly, Omalius d’Halloy (1808) referred to a ‘*terrain bituminifere*’ of France. However, in these earlier works ‘carboniferous’ was a descriptor rather than a construct of stratigraphic division. Conybeare grouped the Coal-measures together with Millstone Grit and Shale, the Mountain Limestone (that contained some coal seams) and Old Red Sandstone. His reasoning was that these strata are so associated together in the same districts that they must be kept together ‘or an inextricable confusion will result’. For these rocks with ‘Carboniferous’ character Conybeare proposed the name of Medial, ‘wishing to adopt an appellation entirely free from theory, and indicating only the central place of this group in the five-fold division of the geological series which results from assigning it to a separate class.’ He added ‘The epithet carboniferous is of obvious application to the series.’ It was that latter term that endured, aided as the re-cast Carboniferous System by John Phillips in 1835.

The book contained few illustrations—just some simple but effective line diagrams and sections—but Conybeare inserted numerous tables with lists of organic remains and sequences and thicknesses of rock. As with Phillips’ earlier books, there was a map, together with a series of cross-sections, also an annexed plate illustrating ‘Geological and Mineralogical Instruments and Apparatus’.

The map was a reduced-scale version of Greenough’s of 1820, but with added lines running across the English Channel to connect the English strata with those on the northern coast of France. Earlier works had attempted such correlation (notably Webster in 1814), but this was the first explicit indication on a map. It may have been inspired by a 1746 map by Guettard mentioned in Conybeare’s introduction, which conjectured how Chalk connected across the Straits of Dover. Conybeare also included, in Book II, a short section on the geology of the coast of France.

The bicentenary of 'Conybeare & Phillips'

Duncan Hawley

Greenough had been generous in sharing the copious notes he had compiled in drawing up his 1820 map. 'Mr Greenough's map' is mentioned on 28 occasions throughout the book, albeit for pointing to both agreement and errors. It might be argued that *Outlines* was *de facto*, a handbook to the Geological Society's large-scale map.

Geological Map, at a scale of 1 inch to 60 miles, with twenty-seven formations (rock groups) recognised. Public domain

The influence

At 470 pages, *Outlines* was the most comprehensive synthesis of stratigraphical knowledge yet attempted and it set the standard for the synoptic description of geology. Its impact was immediate. In his preface to *Outlines of Oryctology*, published the same month, James Parkinson wished his book could be 'considered as a humble subsidiary to that scientific and most valuably comprehensive work *Outlines*'. In 1823 William Harcourt bought several copies for the newly-formed Yorkshire Philosophical Society's library, where they were read by a young John Phillips during his temporary employment there in 1824. De la Beche re-worked *Outlines*' list of formations to characterise the 'English school of geology' in his 1824 synoptical tables. In America, Edward Hitchcock used the book to compare the stratigraphy with emerging American geology, writing that 'We rise from its perusal with an impression that we are now much better qualified to examine the rocks around us than before.' By 1825, the contents and map were being used in a 'less reserved manner' to compile the geology section of a popular knowledge cyclopaedia. In 1828, Fitton declared that *Outlines* 'had an effect to which nothing since the institution of this

[Geological Society] and the diffusion of geological maps of England can be compared.' Darwin took a copy with him on the *Beagle*. Murchison considered it his '*scientific bible*' as he took his first steps in geology. Later, aspects of De la Beche's report on his 'facts' in the first Geological Survey Memoir (1846) would follow a similar style to that found in *Outlines*.

In his seminal 1837 work, *History of the Inductive Sciences*, William Whewell referred to *Outlines* as 'an event far more important than it might at first appear ... The vast impulse which it gave to the study of sound descriptive geology was felt and acknowledged in other countries as well as Britain.' Certainly, two of its geological cross-sections were copied by French cartographer Malte-Brun for Plate 20 in his 1837 *Atlas Complet Du Precis De La Geographie Universelle*, and more than fifty years after its publication, J.W. Judd could still refer to *Outlines* as a 'well-known volume...that held an honorable place among the geological classics.'

Outlines sold several thousand copies, but there was no second printing or edition. In 1828 William Phillips died, and in April of that year Conybeare approached Adam Sedgwick to be his collaborator for the intended 'Part II', 'throwing the primitive and transition rocks together.' The arrangement was to be similar to that of the former volume. Conybeare envisaged that Sedgwick would do much of the work—other commitments precluded him from much fieldwork. But he did also propose to recruit the help of De la Beche, Arthur Aikin on Shropshire, Henslow for north Wales and proposed for himself, De la Beche and Sedgwick to cover the southern part of Wales. Sedgwick had already completed work in Cumbria, to which he would add the Cheviots, Charnwood (estimated to take a fortnight) and Cornwall, about which there was a great quantity of scattered information which required pulling together. If the necessary fieldwork was not conducive to Conybeare's situation, then he would be more than willing to revise and update his introduction on geological theory by gathering facts so as 'to establish on more positive bases the theory of our science.' However the project was suspended following an accident in 1829 where Conybeare was 'thrown out of his gig, and received a dreadful concussion of the brain'. At the same time, Sedgwick became pre-occupied as President of the Geological Society. But when his term of office finished in 1831 he commenced fieldwork in north Wales in preparation for the Part II. However, he was distracted by his ecclesiastical, university duties and other geological matters. Conybeare was similarly busy. Thus, the anticipated completion of *Outlines*, for strata below the Old Red Sandstone, never came about.

Duncan Hawley
duncan.hawley.hogg@gmail.com

Conybeare, W.D. and Phillips, W. 1822. *Outlines of the Geology of England and Wales with an Introductory Compendium of the General Principles of that Science And Comparative Views of Foreign Countries, Illustrated by A Coloured Map And Sections &c.* PART 1. London: William Phillips.

Original copies occasionally crop up for sale, but scanned versions are available online at: archive.org, googlebooks.co.uk and darwin-online.org.uk

A full list of references for this article is available at <https://rb.gy/uvtl8>.

A previously unrecorded letter from Mary Anning, now in the Archive of the Natural History Society of Northumbria, (NHSN), has recently come to my attention. Addressed to Lord Cole, and forwarded by him to William Hutton of the Natural History Society of Northumberland, Durham and Newcastle upon Tyne, it sheds some new light on her clients, the prices of her more common Lias fossils, and on her health.

Lord Cole

William Willoughby Cole (1807–1886), Viscount Cole, from 1840 the 3rd Earl of Enniskillen, seems to have been one of the wealthiest and most enthusiastic customers of the Lyme Regis fossilist Mary Anning (1799–1847). In January 1830, Sussex surgeon and geologist Gideon Mantell, who was yet

William Willoughby Cole (1807–1886), 3rd Earl of Enniskillen, by William Robinson (1799–1839), oil on panel, c.1830 ©National Trust Images.

to meet Anning, had sought Charlotte Murchison's intervention to help him acquire some Lias fossils from Anning, complaining in a letter to Roderick Murchison that 'Lord Cole ... is the grand purloinee and it will be difficult for me I fear to get any without Mrs M's kind interference'. Although Cole's collecting interests were primarily in fossil fish, in 1836 he purchased an

ichthyosaur from Mary Anning which he gave to William Buckland and which is still in the collections at Oxford. His most expensive purchase from Anning was surely that of January 1831 when he is said to

have paid £200 for a juvenile plesiosaur which she had found in December 1830 and which Buckland in 1836 named *Plesiosaurus macrocephalus*.

Cole shared his fossil fish enthusiasm with his close friend Sir Philip de Malpas Grey-Egerton (1806–1881) whom he met when both were students at Christ Church, Oxford, where they attended Buckland's geology classes in 1826. Even before going up to Oxford, Cole had purchased his first specimen from Anning in 1824. He spent the next 55 years adding to his collection. Cole and Egerton visited Mary Anning in Lyme Regis, accompanied her on collecting trips on the beach, and purchased specimens by 'mail order'. The few surviving letters between them and Anning show that they were her friends as well as her clients.

Both Egerton and Cole built up large and important fossil collections that were purchased by the British Museum (Natural History) in the 1880s. Both men were active members of the Geological Society's Council, but Egerton was the more scientifically productive of the pair, publishing over eighty papers, including a combined catalogue of his and Cole's fossil fish collections in 1837. In 1835 Cole turned the south pavilion of the family home, Florence Court in County Fermanagh in Ireland, into a private museum to house his collection of almost 10,000 specimens and invited delegates to that year's Dublin British Association meeting to visit. This may have helped bring some order to Cole's collection; in a letter to Charlotte Murchison in 1833 Mary Anning wrote, 'I do lament with you that Lord Cole does not arrange his Collection, for he possesses specimens as a whole that would be worth any Collector's while to go and see them'.

Cole's interest in and association with Mary Anning spanned sixty years. In 1875, long after Anning's death, Cole acquired the famous B.J.M. Donne portrait of Mary Anning which he presented to the Geological Society, having arranged for it to be sent to the Society by chemist and fossil dealer James Wood Marder (1824–1888) of Lyme Regis. Then, ten years later, just a year before his own death, Cole purchased a portfolio of Mary Anning's papers from her nephew Albert Anning (1842–1902) and sent them to Richard Owen at the BM(NH).

William Hutton

Best known for his 1831–37 *The Fossil Flora of Great Britain* with John Lindley (1799–1865), William Hutton (1797–1860) was a founder, in 1829, of the Natural History Society of Northumberland, Durham and Newcastle upon Tyne, serving as Secretary and as Curator of Mineralogy and Geology until 1847. He joined the Geological Society in April 1828.

Hutton seems to have been in touch with Mary Anning in 1833, perhaps through correspondence or possibly even on a visit to Lyme Regis. In a letter to Charlotte Murchison in October 1833, Anning tells Charlotte that 'Mr Hutton' had

William Hutton (1797–1860). Reproduced from Goddard, T.R. History of the Natural History Society of Northumberland, Durham and Newcastle upon Tyne 1829–1929. Newcastle-upon-Tyne: Andrew Reid & Co., 1929

reported to her that Roderick Murchison’s recent Geological Society President’s Address ‘was the best he had ever heard and that Mr. Murchison looked like a God when he made it’.

On 5 April 1839, Cole, then in Durham, wrote to Hutton enclosing a letter of 1 April which he had received from Mary Anning. Cole’s brief note to Hutton seems to be a response to an expression of interest by Hutton in purchasing a fragment of an ichthyosaur skeleton which Anning had in stock, and about which Cole had enquired on Hutton’s behalf. Referring Hutton to the enclosed letter from Mary Anning, Cole informs him that the ichthyosaur had been sold and that Cole himself had ordered some fossils.

Letters from Mary Anning to Lord Cole, 1 April 1839, and Lord Cole to William Hutton, 5 April 1839

NEWHM: 1996.H390.1 & 2
Rep'd courtesy the NHSN Archive,
Great North Museum: Hancock

J.B.P. Dennis

Anning’s letter tells us that the ichthyosaur fragment was ‘sold to a Mr Denis who is here [in Lyme Regis] during the Oxford Vacation’. This was James Blatch Pigott Dennis (1816–1861) who entered Queen’s College Oxford in 1835 and graduated, and was ordained, in 1839. His interests included ornithology, taxidermy and microscopy as well as palaeontology. He published on the microscopic structure of fossil bone, on the origin of mammals and birds, and on pterodactyl flight. In 1856 Richard Owen described a fossil mammal jaw which Dennis had collected from the Stonesfield Slate of Oxfordshire. Dennis seems to have visited Mary Anning again in June 1843 when he told his friend and fellow fossil-collector the Rev. Thomas Image (1772–1856) about several saurian specimens which she had in stock at that time.

In the 1850s, Dennis was a schoolmaster in Bury St Edmunds in Suffolk and after his death his bird collection was purchased for the Bury Athenaeum and Suffolk Institute of Archaeology and Natural History. The fate of his fossil collection, and of the ichthyosaur fragment he purchased from Mary Anning, is unknown.

Fossil prices

In addition to helping bring Dennis and Hutton to light as Anning clients or prospective clients, and hinting at the possible existence of other unrecognised Anning specimens, this Anning–Cole–Hutton correspondence provides a rare insight into the prices she was charging for some of her less spectacular specimens—the smaller, mainly invertebrate, fossil material that would have made up much of her regular

stock and normal income. Her letter gives a snapshot of at least part of her shop stock at the beginning of April 1839. As we might expect, it comprised typical local fossils: a dozen ‘*Ophiura*’ brittle-stars priced from one shilling to five shillings; specimens of the bivalve *Pinna* from one shilling to seven shillings and sixpence; three specimens of ‘*Loligo*’ fossil squid, but not of the best quality; a slab of *Pentacrinites* priced at £1 5s; ammonites, cut and polished, or rough, from one shilling to 25s; two fish dorsal spines, one almost complete; single ichthyosaur vertebrae; and belemnites, both cut and polished and rough. She gives no prices for the fish spines, the individual ichthyosaur vertebrae or the belemnites. The price of the ichthyosaur fragment in which Hutton had expressed interest but which was bought by Dennis had been discussed in an earlier, now lost, letter to Cole.

The letter also shows that Anning was continuing the practice of cutting (or grinding) and polishing ammonites, as did her father before her, and even extending that technique to belemnites to show their internal structure.

Cole’s note to Hutton indicates that he had ordered ‘some Ophiura Loligos and the Dorsal fins’. Cole’s collection in its entirety was purchased by the BM(NH) in 1882 and 1883 so there is a possibility that these specimens survive, unless they were amongst the specimens stolen at Chester station en route to the museum and thrown into the River Dee. We don’t know whether Hutton ordered any of the specimens listed in Anning’s letter.

Anning’s letter concludes with a comment on her health: ‘I have imprudently done a little to much and have brought a return of the horrible pain in my back’. This personal remark rather implies that Cole knew of her recurrent back pain, and suggests a degree of familiarity between the pair. They had, of course, been acquainted for about fifteen years by this time. Anning’s back pain may simply be attributable to the physicality of her work, lifting and carrying heavy specimens, especially in what was likely to be the confined spaces of her shop. However, it has recently been suggested to me that, as her father died of tuberculosis in 1810, it is possible that her long-term back pain may have been a manifestation of Pott’s Disease, spinal tuberculosis, a symptom of which, in its uncomplicated form, is back pain. We know that she had unspecified health issues from as early as 1822.

Mary Anning’s letter to Lord Cole is a rare survivor of what must have been a significant volume of correspondence with her two wealthiest clients. Any letters to Egerton were most likely lost in a fire in the 1920s at the family home of Oulton Park in Cheshire, while most of Cole’s scientific correspondence was destroyed by one of his successors.

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Tom Sharpe: tom.sharpe1@me.com

'Knocking off' Chomolungma 70 years ago

Douglas Palmer

Douglas Palmer reflects on an historic achievement in the Himalayas seventy years ago this year.

The label, neatly handwritten by the late Bertie Brighton (1901-88), renowned curator of the Sedgwick Museum, is a classic of concise British understatement. It reads **'Highest Rock 40' below summit, Mnt Everest Nepal. E. Hillary (25/3, 75461)'**. Attached is a nondescript centimetre-sized piece of fine-grained and faintly laminated grey rock. However unimpressive it might look, this is one of the Sedgwick Museum's most unique and historically important rock specimens—arguably a terrestrial equivalent of the Apollo 11 Moon rock.

How many young people know the significance of this highest rock sample from the 'roof of the world' and its connection with one of the most celebrated events in British post-war history some 70 years ago?

The awesome rocky edifice of Everest rises nearly 9 km above sea level as part of the

rock wall of the Himalayan mountain range that separates the Indian subcontinent from Central Asia. Historically, the Himalayan range was probably the first to be recognised as one of Earth's major topographic features, being mentioned in a sacred Hindu text, the *Rig Veda* (X:121:4), dating from around 1000 BCE.

Interest in Himalayan geography and geology began in the 19th century. In 1847, the Great Trigonometrical Survey of India, which produced the first measured topographical map of the subcontinent, provided the first estimate of 29,000ft for the height of the highest peak in the range, first known as Peak 'B' and then Peak XV. The height, determined from instrument-based trigonometric triangulation over some 100 miles, was probably calculated by the Indian mathematician and Chief Computer of the Survey, Radhanath Sikdar (1813-1870). It was remarkably accurate.

The name Mount Everest was the result of the British colonisation of the mountain whose Tibetan name is Chomolungma, meaning 'Goddess Mother of the World' and the Nepali name is Sagarmatha meaning 'the Head of Earth touching the Heaven'. 'Mount Everest' was first suggested in 1856 and finally imposed in 1865 in honour of Colonel Sir

George Everest (1790-1866), Surveyor General of India from 1830 to 1843. Apparently, Everest himself objected to the name since he had neither discovered the mountain, nor was his name easily written or pronounced in Hindi.

It was not until the 1920s that the closed kingdoms of Tibet and Nepal allowed access to foreigners and a succession of expeditions began modern scientific exploration and climbing in the high Himalayas. The first modern geological survey was carried out on the 1921 British 'Everest' reconnaissance expedition by A.M. Heron (1884-1971), a Scottish member of the Geological Survey of India. Their remarkable outline map covered some 8,000 square miles (21,000km²) and showed the rocks of the High Himalayas as part of a large 'crystalline complex' flanked to the north by the highly folded Mesozoic strata of the high Tibetan plateau.

Since 1922 several 'official' British attempts to conquer Everest were sanctioned by the Everest Committee of The Alpine Club, interspersed by other nationalities, especially the Swiss. They got within a few hundred metres of the summit in 1952 with one of their lead climbers being a Tibetan Sherpa—Tenzing Norgay. The following year the Nepali authorities allowed the British a ninth attempt with the French and the Swiss having priority for the next two slots.

The British realized that the 1953 expedition was probably their last chance to be first to 'conquer' the mountain. The carefully planned expedition involved some 400 members including 15 climbers, 20 sherpas and 362 porters. It was led by 43 year old army officer and experienced alpinist Col. John Hunt. Base Camp was established at 5,364m (17,598ft) on 12 April and by 21 May, the lead climbers had moved much higher up the mountain ready for a first attempt by Charles Evans and Tom Bourdillon. Using closed-circuit oxygen sets, they reached 8,750 m (28,700 ft) i.e. within 100m of the South Summit, but they had to abandon the attempt when they had problems with the sets and ran out of time.

For the second attempt on 28 May, Hunt selected two men with Everest experience: Tenzing Norgay and Edmund Hillary, a New Zealand bee-keeper and alpinist who had been part of Eric Shipton's British Reconnaissance Expedition in 1951. Using more conventional open-circuit oxygen sets, the pair reached the snow dome summit at 11.30am local time on 29 May. They could not have imagined that the rocks beneath them were ancient seabed sediments originally deposited in the Southern hemisphere some 450 million years ago.

Hillary photographed Tenzing Norgay with his ice-axe raised and the fluttering flags of the United Nations, Great Britain, Nepal and India. Tenzing, a Buddhist, left offerings to the Gods alongside the small crucifix that Hunt had asked Hillary to place at the top. On their descent, at the beginning of the rock face known as 'Hillary Step', it seems that Hillary collected a rock specimen. He was not a geologist, so who or what prompted him to do this? As we shall see, it was almost

*Sedgwick Museum's unique Ordovician limestone specimen recovered from Chomolungma summit by Edmund Hillary on May 29th, 1953
By permission of Sedgwick Museum*

'Knocking off' Chomolungma 70 years ago

Douglas Palmer

certainly in response to a request by the youngest member of the team, George Band.

With Queen Elizabeth's coronation scheduled for 2 June, Hunt and the team knew just how significant their success would be back home in Britain. The problem was how to get the news to London in time for the coronation and before it was splashed over the international press. It was a problem overcome by the ingenuity of the Times reporter James Morris (later and better known as travel-writer Jan Morris), who was embedded with the team.

It was 30 May before Tenzing and Hillary rejoined the awaiting advance party high on the mountain. According to George Band, Hillary's first comment was a characteristically terse and throw away: 'Well, we knocked the bastard off! But this did not reflect his deep respect for the mountain. Morris was also there and immediately typed out a message: 'SNOW CONDITIONS BAD STOP ADVANCE BASE ABANDONED YESTERDAY STOP AWAITING IMPROVEMENT STOP ALL WELL'. When decoded this meant that the 'summit of Everest reached on 29th May by Hillary and Tenzing'.

Without radio connection, the message had to be relayed by runner some 26km to an Indian Army radio station at Namche Bazaar. From there it was telegraphed to the Indian Embassy in Kathmandu, on to the British Embassy in Delhi and thence to the Foreign Office in London where it arrived on the eve of the coronation and in time for the morning papers. Some headlines put the news on an equal footing with the coronation, the Daily Mail had:

THE CROWNING GLORY — EVEREST CONQUERED ...Nature's greatest prize belongs to the Queen this morning

In all the many thousands of words written and broadcast about the climb there is little or no mention of the geology of the mountain nor of the rock that Hillary had pocketed on his way down. From the 1920s geologists became increasingly interested in the structure of the Himalayas and Everest in particular. What were the rocks that formed Earth's roof and how old were they? Heron and Odell thought that the Everest summit rocks formed a conformable sequence above more metamorphosed rocks around the base (from Searle, p.200). Odell mapped the summit pyramid as an 'Upper Calcareous Series' of presumed Permo-Triassic age.

Some 40 years later the geologist Lawrence Wager wrote that 'it never ceases to surprise the writer that the highest point of the Earth's surface is composed of sedimentary rocks that are relatively flat-lying and but little metamorphosed.' He matched the summit rocks with similar rocks in Sikkim and thought they might be of Carboniferous-Permian age. Writing before the advent of plate tectonics, Wager assumed that Everest's summit pyramid had simply been elevated during the uplift of the whole range.

Over the last two decades detailed geological surveying of the region has revealed that low-angle normal faults extend along the entire length of the Himalayas with two in the Everest region. The upper one, the Qomolangma Detachment, is the highest normal fault in the world and cuts

right through the summit of Everest above the marbles of the Yellow Band. Movement along the fault has carried in the generally unmetamorphosed shaley limestones of the summit Qomolangma Formation that Hillary sampled in 1953.

Geology of Chomolungma's summit rocks

(photo M. Searle)

Some 50 years later an international team of geologists showed conclusively that the Qomolangma limestones are of Ordovician age with fossil remains of shallow tropical marine

Crinoid stem ossicle embedded within the Chomolungma summit limestones (photo M.Searle)

life lying deep in the Southern hemisphere.

Relative dating indicates that they are around 450 million years old. Below the fault, the marbles of the Yellow band are of older Middle Cambrian age.

Archival data in the Sedgwick Museum reveal that although the summit rock had been collected by Hillary on that momentous climb, the specimen, along with 31 other rocks from the mountain, was donated to the Museum by Cambridge geology graduate George Band (1929-2011). It is most likely that it was Band who asked Hillary to collect the rock and Hillary was renowned as someone who did what he said he would do. Unfortunately, Band died in 2011 and, so far, it has not been possible to finally verify the story.

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Douglas Palmer
douglaspalmer@gmail.com

Isle of Wight Sand Bells and the mysterious Mr Carpenter

Phil James

In the early 1980s, in a shop window in the Northam Road antiques quarter in Southampton, I spotted a beautiful glass bell filled with coloured sands forming a picture. It didn't have a price, looked expensive, and the shop was, not untypically, closed. I never did go back; but the image stayed with me. Then, ten years later, during a family holiday on the Isle of Wight, we visited Alum Bay to see the cliffs made up of a whole range of coloured sands. In one of the local shops we bought small glass lighthouses which we filled with layers of coloured sand. Our efforts were but a pale reflection of the artistic object in my memory, but then, on a visit to the museum at Blackgang Chine, we saw some more, antique, examples of the craft—fabulous! I became determined, then and there, to find one of my own. Subsequently, over a period of several years, I managed, through eBay, to acquire a number of sand bells, each for just a few pounds. They were fairly basic, showing scenes of the Isle of Wight: The Needles, The Freshwater Arch, Carisbrooke Castle, and others.

Years passed, and then, in October last year, I was in the Salisbury Antiques Market, a treasure trove of antiques arranged over three floors. In one of the cabinets were two glorious sand bells.

Sand bells found at Salisbury Antiques Market (reverse side shown on right)

I could see that these were far superior to those I already had. One had a picture of Carisbrooke Castle, and the other, The Needles. Also, on the reverse, both had a tree depicted in tones of grey—a style, as I later discovered, known as 'grisaille'. They were priced at £33 and £39, and I managed to

Label on base of 'Carisbrook' sand bell

get both for £55: quite a bargain. One had a label underneath—"The natural coloured Sand of Alum Bay, so arranged as to represent Carisbrooke Castle, Isle of Wight, by W. Carpenter. Sold at (blank) by (blank)." The blanks are inked-in **WC** and an undecipherable signature.

are quite something, made with great skill and artistry, using just compacted coloured sand – no glue, no painting, just dry sand! And, of course, they were made upside down! The bases have the sands arranged in a 'marbling' style just like the marbled inside boards and end papers of old books. Above that a coloured band or two and then the picture window. Just look at the detail—"The Needles' bell shows textured chalk cliffs, white crests to the waves, and realistic looking clouds in the sky. Above the picture, one shows simple coloured bands, but the other a series of geometric bands of differing styles.

Late last year, as I searched the internet in preparation for a Zoom presentation on 'The Art of Sand' for the Southampton Mineral & Fossil Society (of which I am currently Chairman, having been a member for over 43 years), I found hundreds of examples of Isle of Wight sand bells, amongst which were a few clearly made by W. Carpenter, the maker of my own examples. Some of these Carpenter bells were plainly identified by a label, but all had that distinctive grisaille fir tree on the reverse. However, very little seemed to be known about this highly skillful artist and I was determined to find out more.

But first, why did this unique form of art first emerge on the Isle of Wight? Plainly, it was the island's geology that had provided Carpenter's raw materials. And for that we have the Alpine orogeny to thank! Without Africa crashing into Europe over millions of years, forming the Alps, and creating a massive ripple reaching 1000 miles to the north, the Isle of Wight would not be as it is today. In simple terms an anticline was formed through what is now the Isle of Wight from west to east. The southern facing dip side now has Cretaceous rocks at the surface, whilst the scarp consists of younger Tertiary strata, and the northern half of the island is covered with still younger beds. As a result, the beds exposed in Alum Bay on the west end of the island are now vertical, with over 1000 feet (305m) of beds, 42 to 56 million years in age.

Alum Bay with brightly coloured sands in the Bracklesham Beds and Bagshot Sands
Photo Roy Starkey

One of the earliest geological maps of the Isle of Wight is by Thomas Webster (1772-1844) in the magnificent 1816 work by Sir Henry C Englefield (1752-1822) *A Description*

The mysterious Mr Carpenter's Sand Bells

Phil James

of the *Principal Picturesque Beauties, Antiquities, and Geological Phenomena of the Isle of Wight*. Webster made a significant contribution with a series of 12 geological letters (chapters) making up well over half the book, plus 36 of the 50 plates including the important geological map—dated 1815, the same year as William Smith's map, but much more detailed. His double page hand coloured plate of Alum Bay is beautiful.

Sir Harry Englefield's lavishly illustrated volume publication, Thomas Webster's geological map and the coloured plate showing Alum Bay

Englefield and Webster both give descriptions of the coloured sands... 'The tints of these cliffs are so bright and varied, that they have not the appearance of anything natural. Deep purplish red, dusky blue, bright ochreous yellow, grey nearly approaching to white, and absolute black, succeed each other, as sharply defined as the stripes in silk', and... 'The number and variety of these vertical layers is quite endless, and I can compare them to nothing better than the stripes on the leaves (? flowers) of a tulip.' It is now generally accepted that there are no fewer than 21 different colours produced through the influence of various iron minerals and carbon.

Another important reason for the appearance of coloured sand souvenirs, both sand bells and pictures, was the increasing popularity of the Isle of Wight as a tourist destination. Queen Victoria moved into a completed Osborne House in 1851. Tennyson and Keats also established homes on the island and other famous visitors included Darwin, Dickens and Lewis Carroll. Substantial villas and hotels were built in towns such as Ventnor, Ryde and Shanklin to house an increasing influx of wealthy visitors, many of whom were keen to buy souvenirs.

So, who was W. Carpenter? By searching through records on Ancestry.com, I pieced together the life of a William Carpenter who first appears in Southampton, then moves sometime between 1844 and 1851 to the Isle of Wight. In Southampton his business is recorded as the 'Southampton Repository of Arts' in the High Street, but is also noted as a Bookseller. In further searches for images on the internet I soon came across this coloured engraving of Alum Bay.

A print of Carpenter's drawing of Alum Bay

Public domain

Drawn by W. Carpenter and published by 'Carpenter, Repository of Arts, Southampton', the caption reads 'In this sublime scene, the vertical strata of many colored sands, the stupendous chalk cliff with its towering light house, and the far famed huge rocks rising boldly out of the sea complete the climax in the charming series of views that increasingly delight the Visitor of Vectian Scenery'.

It was pointed out to me that there was a London-based artist called William Carpenter who produced a fine portfolio of work in both oils and water colour based on travels in Egypt and India—but, although contemporary with 'our' Carpenter, his work was completely different in style. That they were two different people was confirmed when I found six more W. Carpenter engravings, produced around the early 1840s, all showing views and events in the lower part of Southampton near to the location of the Repository of Arts. Clearly Carpenter was a gifted artist and quite able to retail his work.

W. Carpenter's views of Southampton

Imagery ©2023 Google, Map data ©2023
Thumbnails: Public domain

The mysterious Mr Carpenter's Sand Bells

Phil James

I then discovered two further views of the Isle of Wight by W. Carpenter, one of Bonchurch, and another of Carisbrooke Castle which had details strikingly similar to those on the sand bell; both prints were labelled Repository of Arts, Southampton.

Then, finally, the 'eureka' print appeared!

While chatting on the phone last December to fellow HOGG member Martin Simpson—who has himself had a lifetime interest in sand bells—Martin sent across to me the far right hand portion of the following print.

View of Ryde by W. Carpenter

Public domain

I quickly found the whole thing, a splendid view of Ryde, probably dated just after 1846, the year Trinity Church in the view was completed. But, just look at the fir tree in the foreground on the right hand side! It almost looks out of place, but surely it is the very tree that is in Carpenter's sand bells! Like the others, it was drawn and published by W. Carpenter but now there was no mention of the Repository of Arts.

Detail of grisaille tree from 'The Needles' sand bell

Turning back to Ancestry we find that the 1851 Census shows a W. Carpenter, an Artist and Stationer, at 52 High Street, West Cowes together with four of his children, aged 14 to 22, shown as 'Father's Assistant'. Also, although barely legible, a cousin is listed as an 'Assistant in Plastic Art' (anything that could be moulded). Could this have indicated an involvement with the making of sand bells—perhaps fitting the plaster plug? 52 High Street is still a shop today.

By 1859 Carpenter had moved to Ventnor High Street where he is shown as 'Artist' on the 1861 Census. Again, the premises are still a shop today. By 1871 he had moved back to West Cowes and had become a Schoolmaster!

Record	Name	Address	Occupation	Age	Born
1839 Robson's Directory	Carpenter Wm.	60½ High St. Southampton Repository of Arts			
1841 Census	Carpenter, William (Wife Sarah 36)	High Street, Southampton Parish - Holy Rhoad	Bookseller	35	Therefore born c.1806
1844 Pigot's Directory	Carpenter, William	60 High St, Southampton	Bookseller & Stationer		
1851 Census	Carpenter, William (Eldest child 22, therefor married c. 1828)	52 High Street, West Cowes, Isle of Wight SHOP	Artist & Stationer	45	Chichester, Sussex
1859 White's Directory Ventnor Directory	Carpenter Wm.	High Street	Artist		
1859 White's Directory Ventnor Directory	Carpenter Wm.	High Street	Fancy Depot		
1861 Census	Carpenter, William	33 High Street, Ventnor, Isle of Wight SHOP	Artist	55	Brighton, Sussex
1871 Census	Carpenter, William	30 Victoria Road, West Cowes, Isle of Wight	Schoolmaster	65	Chichester, Sussex
1881 Census	Carpenter, William	"Bona Vista" 129 Mill Hill Road, West Cowes	Schoolmaster	75	Chichester, Sussex

So all this evidence, whilst not 100% proven, does point to William Carpenter the artist, being the same W. Carpenter who produced the beautiful sand bells. The fact that he was an accomplished artist confirms to me that he had the skill to create sand bells that were so much better than those of most other makers. The dates of his art, the periods when he was in West Cowes and Ventnor, all tie in with the times when the sand bells were made. Returning to the label on my Carpenter 'Carisbrooke' sand bell, the 'Sold at W C' is almost certainly West Cowes. It's just a pity that the signature is illegible—how wonderful it would be if it matched one of the family names on the 1851 Census!

Epilogue

During my research I also came across a video of the American version of the 'Antiques Roadshow' from Cincinnati, Ohio. Broadcast on 21 July 2012, it featured a huge and incredible Isle of Wight sand bell—nearly 18 inches (45cm) tall, this must surely have been an exhibition piece.

The presenter did not mention a maker, but I thought at once that it was almost certainly by W. Carpenter: similar marbled base and use of 'grisaille' style—though this time featuring Shanklin Chine—on the reverse. But then I

The large Isle of Wight sand bell, now in America

had another 'eureka' moment! Just compare the Alum Bay/Needles sand image with the Carpenter engraving—it's the same boat in the bay, and the cliff profile at the end of the Alum Bay rocks is identical! The American presenter did go on to mention one Andrew Clemens, an incredible sand bottle artist from Iowa.

But that's another story altogether!

Phil James

philip.r.james55@gmail.com

(All images, unless otherwise indicated, are the author's own.)

Frederick J. North: 'a man of ideas, fertile in resources'

Tom Sharpe

Tom Sharpe reveals a little more about the life of Frederick John North (1889–1968).

Reading Dave Williams' delightful account in *GeoHistories* 74 of his inspirational childhood encounter with Dr F.J. North at the National Museum of Wales, I thought it might be of interest to share some further details about North's career.

Fred North joined the staff of the young National Museum of Wales (NMW) on 1 May 1914 as Assistant Keeper of Geology, one of the first curatorial staff to be appointed. The museum had been founded just seven years earlier.

Fred North on his appointment to the National Museum of Wales in 1914.

A Londoner, educated at Beresford Street Higher Grade School in Camberwell, North came to the NMW from King's College, London where he had been a laboratory assistant since 1907, working for Thomas Franklin Sibly (1883–1948), Lecturer in Geology from 1908. At King's College, North not only gained his first curatorial experience through arranging the

geology teaching collections, but studied for an external degree, graduating in 1912, aged 23, with a first in geology. His degree specialisms were palaeontology and zoology, and within a year of finishing his degree he had published his first paper. It was in *The Geological Magazine*, and was on the brachiopod *Syringothyris*.

North's move to the NMW came at the instigation of Sibly who had moved to Wales as Professor of Geology at what was later to become Cardiff University. In January 1913, Sibly suggested to North that he apply for the museum post which was soon to be advertised. In the meantime, North expanded his curatorial experience with a temporary contract to arrange the Palaeozoic mollusc collections at the British Museum (Natural History) under Arthur Smith Woodward (1864–1944).

Following war service from 1917, first in the Royal Army Medical Corps and then the Anti-Gas Corps of the Royal Engineers, in 1919 North was promoted to Keeper of Geology and in 1920 was awarded a DSc by the University of London for a thesis on *Syringothyris* and *Spiriferina*. He was joined by an Assistant Keeper, William Edgar Howarth (1896–1956) in 1921.

The geology collections at the NMW were inherited from the Cardiff Municipal Museum and North set about building them into a national collection through his own fieldwork, through lobbying the extractive industries of Wales for

samples, and through the acquisition of notable collections of individuals. In 1922, for example, he acquired a collection of over 15,000 Coal Measures plants from colliery manager and enthusiastic amateur palaeobotanist, David Davies (1871–1931) of Gilfach Goch, and in 1927 the collection of Griffith John Williams (1854–1933), Assistant Inspector of Mines for North Wales.

Senior staff of the National Museum of Wales 1922. Fred North, second from the left, with the Director William Evans Hoyle (1855–1926) fifth from left, and the Keeper of Archaeology (and later Director 1924–26) on the right, R.E. Mortimer Wheeler (1890–1976).

He was 'an excellent and popular lecturer', according to the NMW Director Cyril Fox writing in 1926, with many and frequent lecture engagements the length and breadth of Wales, speaking to diverse audiences, from professional bodies to local scientific societies and to businessmen's and working men's clubs, his lectures often reported verbatim in the Welsh press.

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Poster for a lecture by North in Aberaman, probably 1930s.

F.J. North: 'a man of ideas, fertile in resources'

Tom Sharpe

North's published output was varied and substantial, with contributions to, for example, *Discovery*, *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, *The Museums Journal*, *The Quarry Managers Journal*, *The Iron and Coal Trades Review*, *The Colliery Guardian* and *Nature* as well as to the transactions of assorted scientific societies and Welsh newspapers. In 1925, the NMW published his first book, *The Slates of Wales* which was followed the next year by *Coal and the Coalfields of Wales*, *Geological Maps* in 1928, *The Evolution of the Bristol Channel* in 1929 and *River Scenery at the Head of the Vale of Neath* in 1930, the same year in which Thomas Murby & Co. published his *Limestones Their Origins, Distribution and Uses* – six books published within just six years. Several of these went on to further, enlarged editions.

North's time at King's College London overlapped briefly with that of Harry Govier Seeley (1839–1909), Professor of Geology there since 1896. North and Seeley seem to have got along well, and after Seeley's death North remained in touch with Seeley's family. Seeley told North of his time as assistant to Adam Sedgwick at Cambridge; Seeley had spent ten years with Sedgwick from 1859, helping in the museum, accompanying Sedgwick on fieldtrips and conducting his own research on pterosaurs from the Cambridge Greensand. Seeley's link to the 'Heroic Age' of geology inspired in North an interest in the history of geology and he set about reading the published biographies of the pioneers of the science, noting as he did so the absence of any biographical account of Henry Thomas De la Beche (1796–1855), founder of what is now the British Geological Survey.

In the 1920s North began a search for De la Beche archives, and success came in 1930 when a box was found in the attic of a house in South Wales belonging to the descendants of De la Beche's daughter Elizabeth. She had married into a prominent Swansea family in 1839. From these descendants, and others in Wales, North acquired for the NMW a substantial collection of De la Beche's correspondence, journals and professional papers. North's interest in De la Beche and the foundation of the Geological Survey led him to borrow the letter books of the Ordnance Survey for 1830–41 which he transcribed and returned in the 1930s. In 1940 the originals were lost when the Ordnance Survey headquarters in Southampton was bombed. North also made contact with two of William Buckland's grandsons who donated letters, some relating to Buckland's research at Paviland Cave on the Gower Peninsula. With this archive now at his disposal, North published a series of papers on the history of geology and the Geological Survey in the *Transactions of the Cardiff Naturalists' Society* between 1933 and 1936, and continued to publish his research through to the 1960s.

In addition to building up the geological collections, North also developed the Geology Department's library, acquiring many classic volumes from the 17th to 19th centuries, and gathered a collection of antiquarian topographical and early geological maps. Between 1929 and 1939, North added over a thousand maps to the collection,

including those of Speed, Saxton, Blaeu, Jansson, Kitchin, Ogilby and Humphrey Lhuys, on whose maps North published a memoir in 1937. The most significant map acquisition was the purchase in 1929 of the collection of Tom Sheppard (1876–1945), Director of Hull Municipal Museum. Sheppard had exhibited his maps at the 1920 Cardiff meeting of the British Association and in 1926, looking to dispose of his collection of British geological maps which he considered 'the finest in existence', made an approach to North. It included maps by Knipe, Walker, Cruchley, Phillips, Murchison, Geikie, Ramsay and others, as well as three copies of William Smith's 1815 map, Smith's small 1820 map and two copies of Greenough's 1820 map – in all, ninety maps purchased for £100. In 1930 and 1931 North added two more copies of Smith's 1815 map to the collection.

Dr F.J. North and his wife, Ellen, seated, on the occasion of his retirement as Keeper of Geology in 1959. Standing behind North is David Emlyn Evans (1914–1997) Assistant Keeper of Geology 1958–79.

For 'services to science in Wales', in 1949 North received an OBE and an Honorary DSc from the University of Wales. North spent the whole of his career at the National Museum of Wales, retiring in 1959. In 1926, however, he seems to have applied, unsuccessfully, for the position of Principal at a new Technical Institute in Wrexham (Denbighshire Technical Institute, now Wrexham Glyndŵr University). In his letter of reference, NMW Director Cyril Fox described North as 'a lucid writer ... a man of ideas, fertile in resources ... a friendly, helpful, and well-liked colleague'. From Dave Williams' experience, it would seem that Fox provided an accurate assessment of the man.

Acknowledgements

I am grateful to Cindy Howells for access to the F.J. North Archive at the National Museum of Wales and for permission to reproduce the images here.

Tom Sharpe
tom.sharpe1@me.com

HOGG's *Cabinet of Curiosities* is a chimerical space combining the personal passion of the classic radio show 'Desert Island Discs' with the broadly educational intentions of the newer programme, 'The Museum of Curiosity'. This exhibit has been donated by Wendy Cawthorne, whose welcoming and expert presence behind the desk in the Geological Society Library is so sadly missed by all historians of geology.

Just over 20 years ago, in October 2002, I was working behind the Geological Society's library counter, in what is now the Lyell Room, when a veritable whirlwind of a man appeared through the door, presented a parcel wrapped in brown paper to me and said, 'The Geological Society must have this for its Archive' before promptly turning to leave. I managed to stop him departing until he had told me who he was and something about the mysterious donation.

The donor identified himself as Dr. Henry Oakeley, then recently retired as a psychiatrist, a Fellow of the Linnaean Society and an orchid specialist.¹ He waited while I opened the parcel which contained an album containing sketches and drawings by none other than Dr. John MacCulloch (1773-1835), one of the Geological Society's illustrious Fellows and its fourth president (1816-1818).

Wagstaff's engraving of MacCulloch's portrait by Faulkner which hangs in the Royal Society <https://gslpicturelibrary.org.uk/john-macculloch-1773-1835/>
(GSL/POR/53/4)

MacCulloch joined the Geological Society of London in February 1808, just 3 months after it was founded. Details of his career can easily be found in books, journals and online, one of the more recent papers being the chapter written by Alan Bowden in the Society's *Special publication*; 317, that had originated as a presentation at one of the Society's bicentennial conferences.

A pre-conservation page from the album of sketches donated by Dr. Henry Oakeley.

Dr. Oakeley was rather embarrassed by the condition of the album since it was rather battered and had been used as a scrapbook by his grandmother, so most of MacCulloch's work was obscured by miscellaneous greetings cards, advertisements from magazines and other such miscellanea. MacCulloch's obituary in the *Annual biography and obituary* said "His skill in drawing was exquisite and the number he has left is very great, independent of those he gave away." What we have in the album are some of the latter.

The bookplate inside the cover of the album was that of Elizabeth Murray (1802-80), granddaughter of the 3rd Duke of Atholl (niece of the 4th Duke). She never married and after her death the book of sketches must have passed to the family of her sister, Atholl Keturah Murray (179?-1844) who had married the Revd Sir Herbert Oakeley, 3rd Baronet, in 1826. Dr. Henry Oakeley is the great-great grandson of Sir Herbert and Atholl Oakeley, making Elizabeth Murray his great-great aunt. Dr. Oakeley said that Elizabeth and her siblings lived with their uncle, the 4th Duke, on the Isle of Man after their

The Cabinet of Curiosities

parents' deaths and it is known that MacCulloch visited the Isle of Man.

The inscription on the title page of the album reads "Born on 4 October 1773 and died 21 August 1835, the effect of an accident, driving alone turning the gig in a narrow lane, the wheels locked, he was thrown out and broke his leg so badly it had to be amputated, he insisted on a few hours thought and preparation, and sank under the operation as he was sure he would do. He was a clever Geologist and Mineralogist and Botanist."

What the author of these words, presumably Elizabeth Murray, failed to say was that the accident happened in Cornwall while on honeymoon with his young wife Louisa née White. His widow continued to promote her husband's work for the rest of her life, and it was she who donated MacCulloch's bust to the Geological Society.

The donated volume was first displayed in the Society in its original state on President's Day, 2003 in the hope that it would generate sufficient interest to raise money to remove the 1950s scrapbook material from the pages and restore MacCulloch's original drawings. The Library Committee suggested to Council that the oil companies drilling in the MacCulloch Field in the North Sea could perhaps be approached to see if they would support the conservation project. To our great joy, they agreed wholeheartedly and paid for the entire work to be done.

The drawings were removed from the original album, mounted on conservation quality paper and bound into two large volumes. These are held in the Geological Society's Archive as LDGSL/ 78/2/8

(<http://geolsocarchives.org.uk/Record.aspx?src=CalmView.Catalog&id=LDGSL/78/2>)

The oil companies, ConocoPhillips, Eni UK and Talisman Energy, who paid for the conservation work are suitably acknowledged on the covers of each volume.

The drawings cover a range of styles from pure sketches and pencil drawings to, in my view, exquisite vignettes, fine pen drawings in oval frames only about 10cm x 6cm, one of which is reproduced here.

One of the oval vignettes.

Wendy Cawthorne

Others are more like caricatures and also those drawn by someone who was mentally disturbed or hallucinating (for an example, see Fig 4 in Alan Bowden's chapter in *GSSP*; 317). Dr. Oakeley pointed out that MacCulloch suffered from malaria, which was rife in Scotland at the time, and no doubt would have taken opium to try to combat or cure the symptoms.

The donation of the volume to the Society fostered my interest in John MacCulloch. At the time no one seemed to have taken an interest in where MacCulloch was buried, so I sent my cousin who lives near Penzance in search of his tomb in Gulval churchyard and he sent me a photo.

MacCulloch's tomb in Gulval churchyard, Cornwall.

Reproduced courtesy of J. Stephen Gould

I enjoyed researching and mounting the exhibition in the Lower Library for President's Day 2003. The brochure I compiled for visitors has been useful in providing details for this article.

Footnotes

1. Subsequently, in 2006, he was awarded the Victoria Medal of Honour by the Royal Horticultural Society for his scientific work on orchids and appointed Garden Fellow by the Royal College of Physicians for his work on medicinal plants, on which he has published several books.

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Wendy Cawthorne
geolibwendy@yahoo.co.uk

A column where historians of geology tell us something of their experience in the field. For this edition we are delighted to welcome Professor Jim Secord.

Jim Secord is Emeritus Professor in History and Philosophy of Science in the University of Cambridge where he has been based since 1992. Equally familiar to students of Victorian literature as to historians of science – for both of whom his seminal work, *Victorian Sensation*, is essential reading – here he tells the story of his geological leanings.

Jim, please tell us how you first become involved in HoG?

I was fortunate to grow up in the United States during a period of great educational expansion and innovation. I was interested in geology even before I could read, and remember books in the early 1960s such as Jane Werner Watson's *Giant Golden Book of Dinosaurs* (1960) that discussed the work of the Bucklands and Mantells. My interest was sparked especially at Pomona College, a liberal arts college where I had two major subjects: English literature and the earth sciences. In geology we used Bob Dott's historically oriented textbook and read many of the great classics of plate tectonics. I remember especially the teaching of Donald McIntyre, who not only was a serious student of James Hutton and his circle, but was also familiar with many of the great names of Alpine geology, as he had studied under Eugène Wegmann at Neuchâtel.

Rather than pursuing postgraduate studies either in literature or geology, I decided to combine the two and become a historian of science. I've always been happy about this choice. My background in literature helped in close reading of texts and their historical settings, and geology provided both training across a wide range of sciences and an understanding of the past on a different scale.

Why is it important to study the history of a discipline like geology?

It has always seemed to me that the best answers to many big questions are historical. This is especially the case in geology, where so much work builds upon deep foundations provided by others, often in the distant past and from different cultural backgrounds. Current work is showing, for example, how much figures such as Alexander von Humboldt, Roderick Murchison and Eduard Suess depended on local informants, indigenous peoples and writings in a wide range of languages. Yet—especially in the sciences—the past is often seen as either irrelevant or an entertaining diversion.

I was privileged to spend my teaching career introducing the history of science to natural scientists, first at Imperial College in London and then at the University of Cambridge

as part of the Natural Sciences Trip. Studying history not only provides students with practical skills in writing and argumentation—it also helps them to appreciate that science is not a fixed body of doctrines or equations to memorize, but a human activity in which they can make a difference. In recent years, I have been pleased to see the increasing interest in geological topics by students in history of science. I remember the historian Roy Porter writing in 1981 (just as I was finishing my Ph.D.) that the history of geology was a 'Cinderella subject', but at last this is no longer the case.

What was your first HoG research project/publication?

After studying at Pomona, I was awarded a fellowship that made possible a year of travel and study in Great Britain, examining the connections between the emergence of geology and the making of the Romantic movement in literature. I attended the Charles Lyell Symposium in 1975, where I met John Thackray, Martin Rudwick, Roy Porter, Gordon Herries Davies, and many other future friends and colleagues. My first paper in history of geology was given at a conference the following summer in Southampton, before I went on to graduate work in history of science at Princeton. My talk was on 'John MacCulloch: Geology and the Appreciation of Landscape', and in it I worked through some of the issues that had led me to study both literature and science. The paper was never published, but writing it helped convince me of the potential for thinking about science historically.

How does HoG relate to your other interests in history of science?

My work in history of geology has always been part of a general interest in the history of the sciences. My first book, which examined the famous controversy between Adam Sedgwick and Roderick Murchison over the boundaries between the Cambrian and Silurian, opened up questions about the role of debate, discussion and communication in science. I've been especially keen to examine issues of reading and reception, as

seen in letters, diaries and records of conversation.

I'm also fascinated by exploring the larger frames we use to tell the story of geology, which (in my view) has been too dominated by accounts that lead to Darwinian evolution or plate tectonics. In recent years I've been glad to see that the practical side of geology has been gaining traction, with more attention given to mineral exploration and resource extraction. Hugh Torrens has championed this view for many years, and he has been proved right.

A HoG's Life

What are your favourite HoG-related books? (and why?)

I realize this is probably cheating, but I would choose the two volumes of Martin Rudwick's collected papers, *The New Science of Geology* (2004) and *Lyell and Darwin, Geologists* (2005). These were published as expensive hardbacks by Ashgate, but are now available as somewhat more affordable paperbacks from Routledge, especially if you can catch them on sale. The level of analysis and evidence in these essays is extraordinarily high, and they are both readable and approachable. I don't always agree with Martin, but he has helped me immeasurably in thinking through the issues.

I'd also recommend two excellent books on the history of geology in China: Grace Yen Chen's *Unearthing the Nation: Modern Geology and Nationalism in Republican China* (2014) and Shellen Xiao Wu's *Empires of Coal: Fueling China's Entry into the Modern World Order* (2015). These books aren't about British or European geology, which has been my own main focus, but they made me re-think the standard stories we tell about geology during the past two hundred years.

What are you currently working on in HoG?

Having recently retired from teaching at Cambridge and directing the Darwin Correspondence Project (now completed in 30 volumes), I'm trying to finish a number of projects, including a study of the Parallel Roads of Glen Roy in Scotland during the 18th and early 19th centuries, when these remarkable features were generally viewed as man-made, rather than as terraces produced by lakes or the sea. The conflicts between the antiquarians, geologists and local Highland residents are really fascinating, and it is a challenge to recreate the circumstances in which the dominant view was that the Roads were hunting terraces for the Kings of Fingal. I'm interested in how things we see as part of 'nature' become that way, and the work it can take to make certain objects become defined as 'geological'. This issue became widespread in colonial and imperial situations during the nineteenth century, as Pratik Chakrabarti has shown in his recent *Inscriptions of Nature: Geologists and the Naturalization of Antiquity* (2020); and it was faced early in the Scottish Highlands, which served as a kind of laboratory for approaches subsequently applied throughout the world.

I'm also currently advising the curators at Edinburgh University Library as they develop an exhibition on Charles Lyell's ways of working (scheduled to open this autumn). Like everyone, I was delighted to see Lyell's notebooks acquired by the University in 2019, along with an extensive collection of letters and other documents. This was after a successful international fundraising campaign, in which HOGG members played a significant role and gave generously.

If Lyell's papers had been more available during the past fifty years, I might well have worked more on him than I did. Helping with the exhibition is both a great privilege and a challenge. For various reasons Lyell isn't as well known to the public as he should be—there is, for example, no popular biography. And it can be challenging to present the core ideas

of his philosophy in a visually striking way. But this was a problem Lyell himself managed successfully in his own lectures and writings, so I am hopeful that the exhibition will be a step on the road to bringing the questions he tackled to a contemporary audience.

Does the history of geology have anything to teach us for the future?

History helps us to see that things change in the past—and helps us prepare for change in the future. The new attention being paid to the role of geology in the exploration of natural resources helps us to understand the forces that have led to the current climate collapse, and to develop ways to communicate what can be done.

Do you have a funny HoG-related story to share with readers?

Many years ago I was interviewed for BBC radio inside the model Iguanodon in the grounds of the Crystal Palace at Sydenham. I'm not sure it's a funny story, but it certainly was my most memorable HoG moment.

The programme involved recreating famous meals in history, in this case the celebrated dinner organized as a New Year's Eve publicity stunt by Benjamin Waterhouse Hawkins.

Dinner in the Iguanodon model, 31 December 1853

London Illustrated News
Public Domain

The re-enacted dinner had to be held on the island rather than in the mould of the Iguanodon, as that was long gone. The presenter Leslie Forbes knew about the naturalist and palaeontologist Edward Forbes, who proved to be a distant relation. A London firm had used Victorian recipes to recreate the different dishes from the original menu. This time the guests ranged from a food historian to the neo-Darwinian philosopher Helena Cronin. The jellies were not a success.

The interview was held in the model Iguanodon. Climbing up through the hole in the belly, I was followed by a large fuzzy microphone on a long pole. Inside it was very dark, so I had to remember without notes all the details of the bricks, mortar and iron rods that made up this remarkable construction. It was, however, a thrill to see the classic words written inside: 'B. Hawkins, Builder'.

What a wonderful story. Thank you so much Jim.

Tourist Bait

Geologist and science writer Nina Morgan celebrates the woman behind Lyme's enduring attraction.

These days few would deny the important contributions made by the fossil collector Mary Anning (1799-1847). With little formal scientific education, but a keen eye for fossils, she combed the beaches around Lyme Regis collecting fossils to sell to tourists. Her extraordinary level of persistence paid off in many ways. After her father's death in 1810, her fossil finds provided her family's main source of income. But it was her discoveries—first, of a series of ever more complete ichthyosaur fossils, and then, in December 1823, of the first complete plesiosaur fossil—that put her name firmly on the map as far as geologists and collectors were concerned.

Mary now has a blue plaque on the wall of the Lyme Regis Museum, built on the site on the site of her birthplace and first fossil shop.

Public Domain

work *Recherches sur les ossemens fossiles*. When she died of breast cancer in 1847 at the age of 48, obituaries were published in various papers and scientific journals in Britain, and her contributions to science were discussed in Henry De la Beche's address at the Annual Meeting of the Geological Society of London in 1848.

Visitor attraction

However, locally in and around Lyme Regis, she appears to have been celebrated more for her ability to attract rich visitors, than her contributions to science. For example, in his magazine, *All the Year Round*, on 11 February 1865, Charles Dickens noted that:

In her own neighbourhood, Miss Anning was far from being a prophetess. Those who had

derided her when she began her researches, now turned and laughed at her as an uneducated unassuming person, who had made one good chance hit. Dr Buckland and Professor Owen and others knew her worth, and valued her accordingly; but she met with little sympathy in her own town, and the highest tribute which that magniloquent guide-book, *The Beauties of Lyme Regis* [a reference to the 1859 2nd edition of *The Beauties of Lyme Regis, Charmouth, the Land-slip, and Their Vicinities*, written by Henry Rowland Brown (Sr) (1837-1921)—a native of Lyme], can offer her, is to assure us that “her death was, in a pecuniary point, a great loss to the place, as her presence attracted a large number of distinguished visitors.”

Quick returns are the thing at Lyme. We need not wonder that Miss Anning was chiefly valued as a bait for tourists, when we find that the museum is now entirely broken up, and the specimens returned to those who had lent them. No one had public spirit enough to take charge of a non-paying concern, when the early geological furore had calmed down, and people came to bathe and not to chop rocks. You may now visit the old abode of saurians without being able to see a single tolerable specimen.

Similar sentiments

A similar sentiment was expressed by Beatrix Cresswell, a writer who is remembered today mainly for her memoirs, local history, antiquarian and ecclesiastical studies, many of which were focused on her home county of Devon. In 1886 she was the author of a charming article which was published in *The Naturalist's World*. It described a fossil hunting trip that she and her sister had taken to Lyme Regis. As she told her readers, once, when rain and rising tide had driven the pair off the beach:

we...indulged ourselves in a visit to the ‘Fossil Shop’, a quaint little house jutting into the principal street, where the tiny space was all too small for the treasures contained therein.

Mrs Dollin told us she had succeeded to the collection of forty years—and some of her fossils may have been found by the celebrated Mary Anning herself. Beautiful they were, filling one's mind with desire, and a wonder whether such treasures ever would come into our possession.

...But in Lyme Regis Mary Anning is nearly forgotten. The people have heard of her, but

Tailings...

they candidly confess that their visitors generally know more than they do. Her grave is in a shamefully neglected and untidy state, and we could not learn in which cottage she had lived, though, after reading a sketch of her life, I strongly suspect that it was no other place than the quaint little fossil shop itself. Her work in aiding science is over, and we can none of us expect more than to do our work well, and rest when it is finished.

Role reconsidered

However, it is clear from a recently re-discovered short manuscript biography of Mary Anning, probably written between 1837 and 1847 while Mary was still alive, that another of Lyme's chroniclers, George Roberts (1804-1860), did recognise her scientific achievements:

Miss Mary Anning fed the impulse given to comparative anatomists which she had first excited. De Saussure, Deluc and others had like some of our great geologists done wonders for geology, but the formation of the earth, as characterized by organic remains, was as yet unknown. This was the period when our country woman began to and went on discovering.

Mary Anning window installed in St Michael's Church, Lyme Regis 1850
Ballista at English Wikipedia, CC BY-SA 3.0

As a sign that her achievements were appreciated by the wider scientific community, within three years of Mary's death, a large stained-glass memorial window was installed in Lyme's parish church by 'the vicar of Lyme and some of the Members of the Geological Society of London'.

Nina Morgan

Statue of Mary Anning
Carbonmoon, CC BY-SA 4.0

More recently Mary Anning has become a modern science icon. Tracy Chevalier's novel *Remarkable Creatures* published in 2009 and the 2020 film *Ammonite* starring Kate Winslet as Mary Anning have both brought Mary to public notice. And the popular campaign, Mary Anning Rocks, which raised money for a statue of Mary to be erected in Lyme Regis, along with the maquette of the statue that is now travelling round the country is inspiring women and girls, in particular, to engage in science.

For those who would like to know more about this remarkable woman, Tom Sharpe's 2020 book *The Fossil Woman* along with various papers by Hugh Torrens and Michael Taylor provide welcome fodder. Reports of previously unrecorded letters from Mary Anning, such as that described by Tom Sharpe elsewhere in this issue, continue to generate great excitement in academic circles—and occasionally eye-wateringly high prices.

Mary's scientific reputation is now, once again, pulling in the tourist trade. Lyme Regis is an important part of the Jurassic Coast World Heritage site; fossils and geology take pride of place in the restored Lyme Regis Museum. Mary Anning's role as tourist bait lives on!

Acknowledgements and References:

Sources for this vignette include: Torrens, H.S, 'Mary Anning (1799 – 1847) of Lyme: "the greatest fossilist the world ever knew"', *British Journal for the History of Science*, vol 28, 1995, pp. 257-84; the article about Mary Anning by Hugh Torrens in *the Oxford Dictionary of National Biography*; the booklet *Mary Anning of Lyme Regis* by Crispin Tickell published in 1996; Charles Dickens, 'Mary Anning, the Fossil Finder', *All the Year Round*, 11 February 1865, Michael Taylor, 'The Cresswell Sisters Go Fossil-Hunting at Lyme Regis in the 1880s', *All Over the Town*, Winter 2022, pp 13 – 16. Michael Taylor and Michael Benton, 2023, *The Life of Mary Anning, Fossil Collector of Lyme Regis: a Contemporary Biographical Memoir* by George Roberts, JGS. Vol 180 (2) doi: 10.1144/jgs2022-053; Tom Sharpe, *The Fossil Woman*, ISBN 978-0-9955462-9-5. I thank Michael Taylor for drawing attention to his article about the Cresswell Sisters.

Nina Morgan
nina.morgan@cooptel.net

Nina Morgan is a geologist and science writer based near Oxford. Her new book, *A Story in Stone: The Geology of the Oxford University Museum of Natural History* is available from the author and via www.gravestonegeology.uk

Future HOGG Events

Thurs 18th May 2023 (Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.00) *A brief history of the geological understanding of the Himalaya* with Dr Daniel Clark-Lowes

Tues 13th June Workshop: *Early production and printing methods of geological maps and illustrations* at the **University of Reading** with Prof. Michael Twyman & Dr Emma Minns (Dept of Typography, University of Reading) (N.B. Places will be limited to 10 HOGG members, please email duncan.hawley.hogg@gmail.com for further details.)

Thurs 15th June (Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.00) *The overlooked early investigations by Adam Sedgwick in northeast England 1821-22: the Magnesian Limestone and the Great Whin Sill* with Dr Doug Holliday

Tuesday 15th - Friday 18th August 2023 HOGG Conference and Field Meeting in Dublin, Republic of Ireland: *Aspects of the history and progress of geology in Ireland* (working title) 1 day conference (Trinity College Dublin) + 3 days field, museum and archives visits, led by Dr Bettie Higgs and Dr Patrick Wyse Jackson (see page 16 of this issue)

Thurs 21st September 2023 (Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.00) *200 years of identifying and understanding former glacial lakes in Britain: a history* with Dr Laura Eddey

Thurs 19th October 2023 (Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.00) *Hogs, vultures, vineyards, ores, volcanoes and quarries in the Northern Carpathians: Robert Townson (1762–1827) and his geological peregrinations in Tatra Mts. and environs* with Dr. Piotr Krzywiec (Polish Geological Institute) and Prof. Krzysztof Marchlewicz (University of Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań)

Tues 21st November 2023 (Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.30) **AGM** – followed by a talk *The Sir Arthur Russell Collection of British minerals – a collection of collections* with Roy Starkey

HOGG Website

Our main website is at <http://historyofgeologygroup.co.uk/>. It will be updated shortly with improved access to all aspects of HOGG, including details of activities & events, online registration, secure Members' area, archived talks, materials and resources and links to cognate organisations. Members will be informed when the revised website is online. We also have a presence at <https://www.geolsoc.org.uk/hogg> where you will find some useful resources.

Social Media

Follow history of geology snippets and selected items of interest to HOGG members through our Twitter feed. Our username is @HOGGGroup. Latest tweets are visible on <http://historyofgeologygroup.co.uk/>, and past tweets can be seen by clicking on the Twitter icon at the foot of that page. All our tweets also appear at <https://www.geolsoc.org.uk/hogg>

HOGG Bulletin

The HOGG Bulletin provides up-to-date news of current and forthcoming events of interest to historians of geology. It is sent out to HOGG members and associates approximately every six weeks via the HOGG Jisc email list.

Please forward all news of events etc. for inclusion to the Bulletin Co-ordinator, Andrew Hopkins at bulletin.hogg@gmail.com

GeoHistories is issued in April and October.

Please send copy by the 10th of the month preceding publication to the editor: Peter Lincoln (hoggnewsletter@gmail.com).

Front Cover: Detail from a sketch of Loch Eriboll by Charles Lapworth (1882-1883)

Image (ref. CL/2/3/6) courtesy of the Lapworth Museum of Geology, University of Birmingham

The geological map used as the backdrop to the *GeoHistories* title was published in 1875. It is a French map from the *Atlas Universel en 67 feuilles* by Brue' and Levasseur (plate No.18.) and is unusual as the projections are centred on Paris and its antipode. The geology on the map is from Jules Marcou's 1861 *Carte Geologique de la Terre* – the second world geological map to be attempted (the first was by Ami Boué in 1843). The great blank areas are due to Marcou insisting he only publish geology that was known rather than based on conjecture. As such, it is an interesting view on the state of geological knowledge in the mid-nineteenth century.

Image courtesy of Duncan Hawley under CC BY-NC 4.0